

Opinion Paper

AI-powered marketing: What, where, and how?[☆]V. Kumar^{a,b,*}, Abdul R. Ashraf^{a,1}, Waqar Nadeem^{a,1}^a Goodman School of Business, Brock University, Canada^b Chang Jiang Scholar, HUST, China; and Distinguished Fellow, WE School, India

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become a disruptive force that has revolutionized industries and changed business practices. The integration of AI has brought numerous benefits to various functional areas within organizations, with marketing experiencing a significant positive impact. AI technologies have empowered marketers with advanced tools and insights, fostering unparalleled efficiency, personalization, and strategic campaign decision-making. Despite these advancements, the scholarly focus on AI's transformative effects on marketing is limited. This research investigates how AI is currently applied across different marketing functions and its potential future evolution and impact on marketing processes. In a rapidly evolving world, businesses must navigate complexity, innovate, and sustain competitive advantages. Grounding our analysis in previous AI marketing literature, we adopt the dynamic capability theoretical lens, emphasizing how organizations adapt and prosper in changing environments. This study highlights six key marketing areas where AI promises transformative effects, aiming to illuminate the path for future marketing innovations and strategies, including AI-driven customer insights, measuring marketing performance, automated marketing strategies, ethical implications, enhancing customer experiences, and growth opportunities with AI implementation. While recognizing AI as a positive disruptive force, we also highlight its limitations, potential threats to privacy and security, as well as ramifications of biases, misuse, and dissemination of misinformation. Finally, the article delineates the gaps in the research and formulates questions aimed at advancing knowledge in AI marketing.

1. Introduction

AI is on the verge of making our lives more productive and creative.

—Bill Gates, Microsoft founder

Artificial intelligence (AI) has gained widespread recognition as a disruptive force that can revolutionize entire industries and bring about significant changes in business practices (Noble & Mende, 2023). Just a few years ago, AI was about robots or futuristic movies, yet here we are, standing on the verge of this imminent reality. Currently, AI solutions are dominant in many user-facing interactions. For instance, AI-powered chatbots influence the online shopping experience by personalizing the experience based on the customer's previous shopping data. Everyday uses of AI include automated customer support for customer queries and requests, and travel assistance wherein chatbots provide users with

travel recommendations, ticket booking, and landmarks recommendations. The growth of AI and its prospects for the marketing industry are immense (Kumar, 2021). In this regard, integrating AI into our daily lives is no longer a question of "if" but rather a matter of "when."

Even though AI is propelling the productivity frontier for economies and businesses across various industries, marketing is undoubtedly one area with the most to gain from AI (Davenport et al., 2020; Huang & Rust, 2021). In an analysis encompassing over 400 AI use cases spanning 19 different industries and nine business functions, global management consulting firm McKinsey & Company determined that AI's most significant potential value is primarily associated with domains related to marketing and sales (Chui et al., 2018). Similarly, in 2022, a comprehensive global survey conducted by Salesforce Research revealed that the utilization of AI among marketing professionals has significantly increased compared to the previous year. The survey indicated that 87% of marketing professionals employed AI to bridge the gap between

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online and offline experiences, a notable increase from 71% in 2021. Additionally, 87% of marketing professionals utilized AI to effectively resolve customer identity, showcasing a rise from 82% in 2021. Moreover, the survey highlighted that 88% of marketing professionals harnessed the power of AI to automate various processes, including reporting, surpassing the 83% recorded in 2021 (Salesforce, 2023). These findings demonstrate the growing reliance on AI within the marketing industry to enhance customer experiences, streamline operations, and drive efficiency. While such industry reports adequately demonstrate the growing importance of AI in marketing, the transformative power of AI in the marketing discipline can be best understood using three illustrative cases from various marketing activities.

First, AI is transforming customer service in various industries. For example, Amazon Prime Air's AI-powered delivery system is a remarkable application of AI that will revolutionize how we experience delivery services. Prime Air aims to deliver packages within 30 min of placing the order. The AI system powering Prime Air constantly learns and improves, enabling drones to navigate diverse surroundings better, adapt to changing weather conditions, and find the most efficient flight paths. This continuous learning ensures that Prime Air evolves and becomes more dependable, delivering packages with unparalleled speed and precision. The AI-powered Prime Air delivery initiative could transform consumers' shopping behaviors and business models as it offers several benefits, such as speed and cost-effectiveness.

Second, the traditional online retail business model follows the shopping-then-shipping model, in which customers place orders before an online retailer ships the products (Davenport et al., 2020). However, Stitch Fix, a multi-brand e-tailer specializing in fashion, and Amazon, with its anticipatory shipping model, have flipped the sequence. By harnessing AI's ability to leverage extensive data, online retailers can make remarkably precise predictions about consumer preferences. This capability paves the way for retailers to shift seamlessly toward a shipping-then-shopping business model (Grandinetti, 2020). For example, Stitch Fix employs an in-house AI system that leverages a combination of customer style, size, price preferences, and non-numerical data (e.g., images) and incorporates insights from other customers who share similar preferences to curate a collection of five articles for each Fix shipment. Customers can keep the items they want and return the ones they do not wish to keep. This shift will enable customers to delegate their buying decisions to the AI application, which primarily makes decisions based on the customer's previous purchases. Consequently, in the age of AI, marketing strategies and business models are evolving from being "reactive" to more "predictive." Although it is too early to draw any firm conclusions, one important takeaway is that AI is a powerful tool for tailoring content, services, and recommendations to individual preferences, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and nurturing long-term loyalty.

Third, marketing core activities involve understanding customer needs, aligning them with the firms' offerings, and convincing individuals to purchase. Traditionally, these activities are spread across different functions (namely, marketing, sales, and service), primarily operating independently. AI can augment a firm's capabilities by facilitating a triple emphasis on marketing, service, and sales, leading to exceptional conversion rates. For example, RedBalloon, an Australian online retailer, utilizes "Albert," an AI-driven digital platform. Albert leverages internal and cross-channel data, customizes creative assets, and buys and manages media space on media channels (i.e., programmatic advertising), including YouTube, Facebook, and Google. It learns and continuously focuses on building a nurturing rather than a transactional relationship. All RedBalloon customers get a personalized experience—thanks to predictive analytics—and the strategically timed questions (i.e., chatbots) help further optimize an engaging experience, leading to higher conversion rates. Given the real-time nature of digital and direct marketing, such automation significantly assists marketers in effectively managing labor-intensive, high-time-pressure processes. However, the risk has been heightened for employees as automation will

likely replace many jobs. Similarly, companies may experience negative consequences as customers may not be receptive to or feel at ease knowing they are interacting with a bot.

The above three examples demonstrate that AI has moved beyond being a concept of the future; it has become an integral part of our daily lives. Both academics and industry professionals have high expectations for the impact of AI on marketing strategies and customer behaviors. In practice, many marketing functions have implemented AI applications, such as chatbots for enhanced customer experience, predictive analytics for lead scoring, churn prediction, and campaign optimization, recommendation engines for personalized content and product recommendations, content creation for social media posts and email campaigns, natural language processing for customer sentiment and feedback analysis, and programmatic advertising for buying and optimizing digital advertising space in real-time, among others (Kumar, 2021).

On the academic side, we observe AI research's proliferation in marketing. For example, the impact of AI-powered robots on frontline employees and consumers' shopping behaviors (Bonetti et al., 2023; Holthöwer & van Doorn, 2023; Maragno et al., 2023; Mende et al., 2023); psychological and cultural barriers to the adoption of AI shopping systems (de Bellis & Venkataramani Johar, 2020; De Bruyn et al., 2020); ethical concerns in implementing autonomous shopping systems (Hermann, 2022; Kim et al., 2023); influence of AI chatbots on in-store and online customer experience, customer service (Grewal et al., 2020; Puntoni et al., 2021; Zierau et al., 2023), and investor sentiment (Fotheringham & Wiles, 2023; Rust & Huang, 2021); application of different machine learning techniques, such as text, voice, and emotion analyses (Guha et al., 2023; Han et al., 2023) and dynamic online pricing (Misra et al., 2019); and leveraging extensive data to optimize online consumer profiles and searches (Duan et al., 2019; Haleem et al., 2022; Vaid et al., 2023).

While the application of AI in marketing is gaining popularity in practice, it is not surprising, given its relative newness and complexity, that its role across different marketing functions seems to be under-investigated—although not completely overlooked (Ameen et al., 2022; De Bruyn et al., 2020; Huang & Rust, 2022a). This prompted the current research to examine the extent to which AI is used across various marketing functions (i.e., *what* and *where*) and *how* it will likely evolve and impact future marketing strategies and customer behaviors. Our research is grounded in the dynamic capability theory (Hunt & Mahavaram, 2020; Kumar et al., 2019; Leemann & Kanbach, 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Teece, 2020; Weaven et al., 2021). By integrating this theory, we align our investigation with a significant theoretical perspective and address the growing demand for a deeper comprehension of how artificial intelligence (AI) influences marketing practices. This approach responds directly to calls for in-depth research into the interplay between AI and marketing, as highlighted by Huang and Rust (2022a) (2022b) and Mishra et al. (2022). Our study endeavors to reveal AI's capacity to transform marketing strategies and operations, emphasizing the critical role of dynamic capabilities in navigating the evolving landscape of technology-driven marketing.

Building on this theoretical foundation, we conducted a thorough literature review on AI's role in marketing (see Table 1), complemented by insights from 40 marketing professionals in middle to senior management roles. This dual approach helped us identify six key marketing themes that are essential for understanding AI's transformative effect on the marketing landscape. These themes, detailed in Fig. 1, underscore AI's potential to revolutionize marketing through enhanced personalized customer insights, automation of marketing strategies, and more efficient operations. Our findings not only summarize the current state of AI in marketing but also chart a course for future research and developments in this rapidly evolving area, illustrating the broad and impactful possibilities for AI's integration into marketing practices.

Table 1
Recent select studies on AI in marketing.

Authors and year published	Journal	Conceptual framework
Kumar et al. (2019)	California Management Review	Conceptualizes personalized engagement marketing as an approach to creating, communicating, and delivering personalized offerings to customers using AI.
Huang and Rust (2021)	Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science	Conceptualizes cyclical methodology for strategic marketing planning by incorporating multiple AI benefits.
Whittaker et al. (2021)	Australasian Marketing Journal	Conceptualizes a framework for deepfake in the marketing literature.
Mogaji and Nguyen (2022)	International Journal of Bank Marketing	Conceptualizes a framework for adopting AI for financial services marketing.
Perez-Vega et al. (2021)	Journal of Business Research	Conceptualizes online customer engagement behavior based on the stimuli-organism-response (S-O-R) theory.
Huang and Rust (2022a)	Journal of Retailing	Conceptualizes “collaborative intelligence in marketing,” emphasizing the cooperative relationship between AI and human intelligence.
Chen et al. (2022)	Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing	Conceptualizes a framework for AI adoption in business-to-business marketing.
Ngai and Wu (2022)	Journal of Business Research	Conceptualizes a framework for machine learning application in marketing.
Plangger et al. (2022)	Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science	Conceptualizes a framework for the conversion of strategic resources into value for customers, companies, and society.
Ameen et al. (2022)	Psychology & Marketing	Conceptualizes a framework regarding the antecedents, dimensions, and outcomes of creativity in marketing and AI.
Mariani et al. (2023)	Technovation	Conceptualizes a framework on the drivers and outcomes of AI adoption for innovation.

2. Role of AI-powered marketing

2.1. Overview of AI in the marketing field

Artificial intelligence (AI), characterized by powerful algorithms and machine learning capabilities, has revolutionized marketing (Noble & Mende, 2023). Haleem et al. (2022) define AI as a technology that allows computers to simulate and comprehend human interaction and behavior, whereas Haenlein and Kaplan (2019) define it as a ‘system’ that can analyze external data, gain insight from it, and then employ what it has learned to achieve specific objectives and tasks through flexible adaptation. Mustak et al. (2021) also consider AI as an umbrella that spans numerous activities and concepts under the wide-ranging belief that various computer systems, through the application of software and algorithms, can support or undertake tasks that once demanded human cognitive skills.

AI in marketing is synonymous with precision, personalization, and efficiency (Huang & Rust, 2022a; Yu et al., 2019). It empowers marketers to customize their efforts to match consumers’ requirements and preferences, thus promoting more meaningful and productive interactions (Tiautrakul & Jindakul, 2019). AI’s eponymous intelligence originates from its ability to self-learn and continuously improve itself, increasing its productivity and efficacy with each task iteration (Verma et al., 2021). It can automate routine and non-routine operations by simulating human thinking and actions, evaluating complicated data to uncover behavioral patterns and insights, and learning from experiences to make intelligent decisions (Huang & Rust, 2018). Generative AI is an

example of a tool to generate content and ideas for almost 50% of marketers in the industry (Rodrigue, 2023).

Adidas and Netflix exemplify the broad applications of AI in the business realm. Both companies use AI to analyze vast amounts of consumer data to identify patterns, trends, and insights that can inform marketing strategies and campaigns (Mathur, 2023; Prentice et al., 2020). To improve its marketing budget, Accenture uses AI to optimize data collection, reducing the data flow process time by 80% (Mishra et al., 2022). This has helped the company cut the insight lag from 5 months to 5 weeks, enabling Accenture to gain an additional \$300 million in sales without increasing media spending (Accenture, 2024).

Moreover, AI finds intriguing applications in observing customer behavior and habits even after the purchase. In this regard, P&G implemented intelligent faucets in the residences of willing participants to monitor product utilization (Cretella, 2022). The provided insights revealed actual water-saving benefits of dishwashers, despite the misconception that these machines are energy-consuming. Following these insights, the marketing team launched the “Do It Every Night” campaign, helping to increase the knowledge (Business Wire, 2020). The campaign led to an increase in weekly dishwasher usage, promoting both sustainability and business growth.

Overall, the advancement in AI technologies and capabilities has fundamentally changed how marketers connect with customers, understand their requirements, and offer value (Kumar et al., 2019; Kumar, 2021). It serves as a ladder between technology and marketing to promote innovation, improve consumer experiences, and achieve superior marketing results (Huang & Rust, 2021). Although AI’s rapid evolution involves ethical concerns such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and misleading predictions, strong guidelines and regulations can alleviate the challenges (Elliott & Soifer, 2022; Manyika et al., 2019). Integrating AI into marketing techniques can be regarded as a symbol of transition toward data-driven and consumer-centric methods and offers a future in which marketing is more responsive, adaptive, and effective.

2.2. Early adoption of AI in marketing

Initiated in the 1940s and influenced by Alan Turing’s code-breaking device and Isaac Asimov’s robotics laws, the historical trajectory of AI has gone through several seasons, each with its developments and challenges (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). However, until the early 2000s, the notion of AI in marketing was still in its early stages when corporations began researching data mining techniques to better understand customer behavior and preferences (Aflalo, 2020). Customer segmentation, targeting, and positioning were the primary goals of early applications. Email marketing systems began to use AI to improve sending times and email content, leading to increased open rates and engagement. With the rise of search engines such as Google, the use of AI has become critical in building algorithms for search engine optimization (SEO) and pay-per-click (PPC) advertising (Danao & Main, 2022). Marketers began to optimize keywords, bids, and ad optimization, hence increasing visibility and click-through rates (Schwartz, 2022). This was also the era of programmatic advertising, which enabled automated, real-time auction ad buying while targeting users with greater accuracy and at scale (Das, 2023).

In the late 2000s, the growth of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter opened new avenues for AI. Marketers have slowly begun to use AI-powered tools for brand monitoring, sentiment analysis, and social media management and analytics (Kaput, 2022). Firms employed these tactics to gain insight into customer sentiments and trends to design more personalized and adaptable marketing campaigns. With the surge of Big Data in the 2010s, AI-powered predictive algorithms were able to forecast future behaviors and trends by analyzing customer behavior, purchase history, and interactions (Simpson, 2020).

In the 2010s, the introduction of chatbots and virtual assistants such as Siri and Alexa was a turning point in AI-driven marketing (Kaplan &

Fig. 1. Marketing areas where AI can bring about transformative effects.

Haenlein, 2019; Verma et al., 2021). These AI-powered tools made immediate, personalized interactions with shoppers possible. In the late 2010 s, advances in machine learning and deep learning facilitated more complex and autonomous AI applications in marketing. The processing and analysis of unstructured data, such as text and photos, enabled improved content and visual recognition (Qin & Jiang, 2019).

As we move through the 2020 s, the use of AI in marketing has advanced from simply a technological aid to a key engine of cutting-edge tactics. Now, more AI-powered marketing applications that have been developed for specific uses are being used by companies. Table 2

Table 2
Select AI applications in marketing.

Selected AI Applications	Key Players
Data Science Platforms	SAS, IBM Watson, Rapidminer, Anaconda
Data Generation & Labelling	Hive, Upwork, Amazon M-Turk, Unity
Machine Learning Operations (MLOPS)	Fiddler, Arize, Neural Magic, Evidently AI
Computer Vision	Amazon SageMaker, Matroid, clarifai
Speech	Siri, Alexa, Cortana, PolyAI
Natural Language Processing (NLP)	Google Cloud Natural Language AI, Hugging Face, Amazon Translate
Edge AI	Hailo, Deeplite, Edge Impulse
Horizontal AI/AGI	Google Research, Microsoft Research, Meta Research, OpenAI, stability.ai, Midjourney
AI Hardware	Google Cloud, Nvidia, Intel, Graphcore, Cerebras
Closed Source Models	OpenAI (ChatGPT), OpenAI (DALLE2), OpenAI (GPT-4), DeepMind, Midjourney, Google Bard, Google LaMDA

Source: Insights Compass 2023 - Unleashing Artificial Intelligence's true potential. In *Statista*. Retrieved September 04, 2023, from <https://www.statista.com/download/MTY5Mzc0Njk0MiMjMjIwMjY0OCMjMTM4OTcxIyMxIyNudWx5IyNTdHVkeQ==>.

provides a selected list of AI applications and the companies operating in this space. Technologies, such as predictive analytics, have been essential in forecasting customer behavior, allowing marketers to develop strategies that are not only responsive but also proactive (Haleem et al., 2022). Programmatic advertising, powered by AI, has enabled marketers to navigate the fragmented digital advertising landscape, automating ad buying processes and optimizing ad placements in real time, ensuring that ads reach the right audience at the right time (Ford et al., 2023). Combining AI with cutting-edge technologies, such as metaverse, augmented reality, and blockchain, is anticipated to open new possibilities and boundaries in digital marketing (Noble & Mende, 2023). Marketers face both a challenge and an opportunity in harnessing these technologies to develop innovative, personalized, and ethically responsible marketing strategies that resonate with the increase.

2.3. Theoretical frameworks underpinning AI in marketing

The convergence of AI and marketing signals a transformative era in the modern business landscape, redefining conventional concepts of customer engagement, data analytics, and strategic decision-making (Laker, 2023). With its substantial impact on redefining marketing, AI has drawn attention for its ability to transform marketing practices and consumer engagement in a progressively digital realm. As it becomes a sophisticated staple in marketing activities, AI demands a rethinking of practical strategies and a refinement of the theoretical frameworks in marketing literature (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). This section aims to create a theoretically solid foundation for future research and practice by providing a concise overview of AI's theoretical underpinnings and real-world applications in marketing. Despite the vast literature on AI in marketing, which spans various topics and technologies, we briefly dive into some prominent conceptual frameworks in this domain.

One theory that carefully outlines AI's role in marketing is presented

by Huang and Rust (2021), which integrates a three-stage strategic planning framework inspired by Deming's (1986) plan-do-check-act cycle. This approach offers a cyclical methodology for strategic marketing planning, starting with detailed marketing research, developing segmentation, targeting, and positioning strategies, and executing specific marketing actions, which then inform future marketing research, creating a continuous cycle. Huang and Rust (2021) underscore AI's vital role across all three strategic marketing stages, pointing out various AI intelligences: mechanical, thinking, and feeling, each mimicking particular human abilities and applied across different tasks (Huang & Rust, 2018; Huang et al., 2019). Mechanical AI focuses on automating routine tasks, thinking AI processes unstructured data to make decisions, and feeling AI is designed to interact with humans and/or analyze human emotions.

In another study, Huang and Rust (2022a) introduce "collaborative intelligence in marketing," emphasizing the cooperative relationship between AI and human intelligence (HI). The framework includes marketer and consumer intelligence in performing marketing and consumption tasks. It outlines three general principles (GP) to explain how collaborative intelligence can be achieved in marketing at various intelligence levels. GP1 highlights the unique strengths of AI and HI, GP2 suggests that lower-level AI should enhance higher-level HI, and GP3 proposes a progression whereby AI first supports and then replaces HI at each intelligence level, promoting collaboration to move to a higher intelligence level when AI can autonomously perform all lower-level intelligence tasks.

A compelling study by Plangger et al. (2022) highlights the transformative impact of emerging digital technologies in formulating strategic marketing and generating value for customers, firms, and society. The researchers introduce a framework that emphasizes employing strategic resources, including financial, human, technological, and customer data, to develop and implement relevant digital technologies such as Metaverse, Robotics, IoT, and virtual assistants. This approach achieves strategic outcomes benefiting customers, firms, and society. They further categorize strategic outcomes into customer value (i.e., satisfaction, repurchase intention, acquisition, and word of mouth), brand value (i.e., sales performance, competitive advantage, market share, and brand reputation), and societal value (i.e., ecological regeneration, stakeholder stewardship, and governance leadership). This study also introduces AI as a boundary condition that mitigates the investments of strategic resources in the aforementioned emerging technologies.

Perez-Vega et al. (2021) conceptualize online customer engagement behavior, providing a conceptual framework based on the stimuli-organism-response (S-O-R) framework, aiming to explore integrating customer interaction with AI in marketing. The concept defines stimuli as solicited and unsolicited manifestations of online customer engagement behaviors that drive the AI organism process, resulting in AI and human responses. The stimuli are processed by AI organisms, which can deliver real-time insights and action suggestions. For more comprehensive real-time customer insights, the AI organisms combine live and stored data using various data processing methods, including content-based, collaborative, and hybrid methods. Real-time customer data are used to inform the responses, which can be manual or automated company responses. Sentiment and category analysis can produce more comprehensive results on future online customer engagement behavior. This framework aims to pave the way for further research into the uses and implications of AI in enhancing and developing customer and company interactions in a marketing context.

Other prominent frameworks in this domain include a framework for understanding the role of AI in personalized engagement marketing and offering predictions on two key strategic firm assets—brands and customers—across developed and developing economies (Kumar et al., 2019), a framework for AI adoption in business-to-business marketing (Chen et al., 2022), a framework for machine learning application in marketing (Ngai & Wu, 2022), a framework of the drivers and outcomes

of AI adoption for innovation (Mariani et al., 2023), a framework of adopting AI for financial services marketing (Mogaji & Nguyen, 2022), and a framework regarding the antecedents, dimensions, and outcomes of creativity in marketing and AI (Ameen et al., 2022). These frameworks serve as road maps for AI-powered marketing in different domains prevalent in the current era. However, our focus remains on the most recent and relevant AI issues critical for improvements in the marketing area, which we will discuss in the following section.

2.4. AI-driven marketing capabilities

Implementing AI has demonstrated a significant enhancement in firms' capabilities across various industries (Kumar et al., 2019). Dynamic capabilities theory has long been the fundamental basis of firms seeking sustainable competitive advantage (Teece et al., 1997). Organizations with dynamic capabilities can quickly innovate, modify, and reorganize their business plans and procedures in response to emerging technology, altering consumer demands, and changing market conditions. In this era, AI has emerged as a pivotal dynamic capability, embodying the transformative power of technology in business strategy (Agarwal et al., 2021).

AI-driven capabilities refer to the skills, functionalities, and strengths that are enabled or greatly empowered by AI across a range of domains (Sjödin et al., 2021; Agarwal et al., 2021). These capabilities extend beyond traditional firm capabilities and resources, leveraging data analysis, automation, decision-making, and adaptive innovation to amplify responsiveness to market changes (Mariani et al., 2022; Mikalef & Gupta, 2021; Teece, 2019; Vlačić et al., 2021). For example, AI-driven capabilities integrate advanced algorithms for predictive analytics, automate tasks, and tailor messages to individual consumer profiles (Shovo, 2021). This fosters a nuanced understanding of customer needs, leading to more efficient and impactful marketing efforts (Ameen et al., 2021). Hence, AI-driven capabilities are not just an upgrade to existing methods but a transformative approach that redefines the landscape of modern marketing.

Building on past AI marketing research (e.g., Kumar et al., 2019), we delineate AI-driven marketing capabilities into three main categories: *analytical marketing capabilities*, *technological marketing capabilities*, and *strategic efficiency capabilities*. *Analytical marketing capabilities* refer to the ability to use AI for deep analysis of large and complex datasets (Adi et al., 2020). This capability involves extracting insights from customer data, market trends, and consumer behavior (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019), enabling firms to examine the effectiveness of their performances in the form of marketing campaigns or ad placements (Campbell et al., 2020). *Technological marketing capabilities* focus on the integration and application of AI technologies to enhance brand offerings (Mariani et al., 2022). It includes the incorporation of AI tools and platforms to automate marketing processes and create intelligent marketing content, all while ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines. Lastly, *strategic efficiency capabilities* encompass more than just improvements in efficiency; they include initiatives aimed at increasing the agility and responsiveness of marketing operations to adapt to changing market dynamics and shifts in consumer preferences, such as engagement with emerging realities like the metaverse and spatial computing. These capabilities provide enduring benefits and are instrumental in significantly enhancing the customer experience (Mikalef & Gupta, 2021). In the following sections, we delve deeper into the three AI-driven marketing capabilities.

2.5. Marketing themes and AI-driven capabilities

Following a comprehensive examination of current trends, a survey with 40 marketing professionals at middle to senior levels, and an extensive literature review (see Table 1), this paper has identified six marketing themes that are explored under each capability presented in the previous section. These themes offer a pivotal understanding of the transformative impact of AI on the marketing landscape (Fig. 1). The

organization of these themes reflects their relevance to each discussed capability and has been drawn upon a broad range of studies that have investigated AI's contribution to marketing. For instance, Al Mubarak and Hamdan (2023) contribute to our understanding of the depth and breadth of AI's role in marketing. Haleem et al. (2022) outline the significant applications of AI in marketing, while Anayat and Rasool (2024) analyze keyword co-occurrence and co-citation to delineate principal topics and research areas in AI for marketing. Additionally, Verma et al. (2021) conducted an extensive literature review, providing organization to the existing body of work on AI's role in marketing.

To complement our literature review, we surveyed to determine the practical importance of AI in the six identified marketing themes further. Therefore, we administered an online survey to 40 marketing professionals (middle to senior management positions) in companies currently implementing or considering the integration of AI in their marketing, sales, or advertising activities. The survey reveals that the "Ethical Implications" of AI in marketing emerged as the most significant theme. Its rating and ranking scores surpass those of the other themes, highlighting the critical importance of ethical considerations in AI applications. The results of this survey are discussed in more detail in the following sections.

In the curation of these themes, meticulous attention was paid to ensure distinctness and minimal overlap among them. We intended to isolate themes that were most salient and impactful within the marketing domain, specifically those that underscored the transformative role of AI. Initially, nine themes were identified, and upon recognizing overlaps, this was refined to six distinct themes. However, it is acknowledged that this thematic exploration is not exhaustive. The dynamic nature of AI and its growing influence in marketing suggest numerous other potential themes that can be explored in future research.

To provide deeper insights into AI's role in marketing, we systematically explored each AI-driven marketing capability (analytical, technological, and strategic efficiency) through two corresponding themes. These themes highlight critical aspects of each capability and present a comprehensive understanding of the potentials and challenges of AI's role in marketing. Furthermore, the themes present crucial considerations for managers, highlighting critical areas of focus during and after the integration of AI in marketing strategies. They underscore the challenges that managers should anticipate through the ongoing use of AI in their marketing operations. This structured thematic approach equips practitioners with valuable insights for effectively integrating AI into their marketing practices while confronting its complexities and optimizing its benefits.

2.5.1. Analytical marketing capabilities

Analytical marketing capabilities offer AI-based analytics centered on customer data. This capability is studied through two themes: AI-driven customer insights and measuring marketing performance. AI-driven customer insights focus on using AI to streamline customer relationship management via data insights and predictive analytics, as well as implementing algorithmic personalization and customer segmentation (Mariani et al., 2022; Huang & Rust, 2021). This approach enhances the effectiveness and relevance of marketing strategies by deeply understanding customer data and preferences. In the case of measuring marketing performance, the emphasis shifts toward leveraging AI in two significant ways: the application of AI-powered analytics tools for executing marketing initiatives and the employment of real-time performance tracking to enable agile, data-informed decision-making (Rosário & Dias, 2023).

2.5.1.1. Theme 1: AI-driven customer insights. Diving into consumer behavior, analytical marketing capabilities harness the power of AI to meticulously analyze patterns and predict future actions (Fan et al., 2023; Lalicic & Weismayer, 2021). These predictions allow marketers to

navigate through the customer's journey strategically. AI redefines customer relationship paradigms by anticipating consumer demands, tailoring interactions, and optimizing customer journeys through predictive analytics. For example, AI analyses of customer retail checkout data help marketers gain insights about consumer needs and preferences, leading to increased satisfaction and purchase likelihood through real-time personalized communication (van Esch et al., 2021).

Moreover, AI-powered customer relationship management (CRM) systems can evaluate historical purchase data to predict future purchasing behaviors, allowing firms to develop focused marketing campaigns that increase client loyalty and revenue (Chatterjee et al., 2019). The enhanced personalization and predictive capability create a more engaged and loyal customer base, as consumers often respond positively to brands that understand their needs and preferences (Arora et al., 2021). This paper's introductory theme focuses on AI-driven customer insights, a critical component of analytical marketing capabilities. Specifically, it focuses on two key aspects, namely (a) predictive analytics emerging from AI-enhanced CRM and (b) algorithmic personalization and segmentation of customers. We go deep into the application of these elements, exploring their advantages and disadvantages, and subsequently illuminate the discussion with pertinent examples.

Predictive analytics (CRM).

AI-powered CRM systems help firms identify potential consumers and strengthen relationships with existing ones (Taryn, 2023). These platforms aim to generate leads, convert potential customers into actual buyers, and maintain engagement with the existing customer base across various channels. To achieve these objectives, marketers undertake specific initiatives and operations, which are now more streamlined than ever with the help of AI. Predictive algorithms facilitate campaign management, data analysis and reporting, email management, lead scoring, customer categorization, and conversation and sentiment analysis (Fotheringham & Wiles, 2023; Guha et al., 2023; Han et al., 2023). For campaign management, generative AI suggests headlines and adjusts the tone of communications, while AI ad management selects the optimal demographics and the most effective platform for outreach (Simonsen, 2022). Meanwhile, natural language processing (NLP) algorithms offer insights into customer sentiments during conversations and predict the best approach for further interactions (Ma et al., 2018).

The predictive analytics assess user interactions with email content, enable better predictions on send times and content customization, and prioritize customer support based on the content (Ashbridge, 2023). Call tracking AI platforms such as Talkdesk can unlock stories behind conversations. Talkdesk extracts valuable insights from call recordings, refines the data, and integrates it to create a comprehensive customer profile, allowing for the delivery of high-quality customer service. This multidimensional use of AI in the digital activities of CRMs not only optimizes business processes but also significantly improves customer relationship and interaction management (Buchanan, 2023).

Moreover, AI insights pinpoint prospects with a high likelihood of conversion and recommend subsequent actions based on historical performance (Noble & Mende, 2023). Marketing strategies can be adjusted to target high-potential prospects more effectively based on their preferences and behaviors (Harvard Business Review, 2023). Automated reminders can also be set for the sales team to follow up at optimal times, ensuring no missed opportunity. Einstein AI is an example in this regard, which identifies prospects with a high likelihood of conversion based on historical interactions and performance metrics. For instance, Einstein might advise a targeted follow-up email or send a limited-time offer if a prospect frequently interacts with email campaigns but has not purchased it yet. Such processes are not limited to the B2C context and can be implemented in B2B marketing (Kim & Kumar, 2018), where the sales cycles are typically longer and more complex. In these environments, AI-powered CRM systems are invaluable for nurturing leads through prolonged decision-making processes. They offer tailored content delivery and automated follow-ups based on individual lead behavior and preferences, enhancing the chances of

conversion.

Apart from digital marketing activities, AI's capacity to detect patterns in client sales data enables it to deliver more accurate sales projections and allows organizations to strategically plan and enhance their sales operations (e.g., Rohaan et al., 2022; Sohrabpour et al., 2021). IBM's use of its AI platform, Watson, in its CRM systems is an industry example (IBM (n.d.)). IBM Watson helps organizations find patterns and correlations between various factors that could affect sales, including seasonal changes, promotional activities, and shifts in customer preferences. Watson can give merchants more precise sales projections, empowering them to make wise choices about their inventory, marketing plans, and customer interaction. This predictive capability helps retailers optimize their operations, reduce costs related to overstock or stockouts, and enhance customer satisfaction by ensuring that desired products are available when needed.

Although the ability to forecast consumer behavior and trends has changed CRM, predictive analytics has limitations and drawbacks (e.g., Brynjolfsson et al., 2021). The reliability and accuracy of the data are critical components of predictive analytics. Inaccurate projections can be made due to inaccurate or inadequate data, which leads to the formulation of poor business plans and decisions. Data integrity is, therefore, crucial, yet consistently maintaining high-quality data can be challenging and time-consuming. Similarly, manipulative marketing strategies have been in use for a long time. However, these strategies, when combined with the extensive amounts of data for AI predictive algorithms, have far expanded the capabilities of what firms can do to drive users to choices and behaviors that ensure higher profitability (Bansal, 2021).

Therefore, while predictive analytics can provide valuable insights, they should be used to supplement rather than replace human decision-making, at least at the current stage of technological advancements. A lack of human oversight can lead to an over-reliance on technical projections, which may fail to account for unforeseen variables or contextual nuances.

Customer segmentation and personalization.

Customer segmentation has long been a popular area of research, as marketers have always aimed to sell the right product to the right customer. The advent of AI has, therefore, been a game-changing factor that can make dreams come true. Using AI to segment customers and customize services to their specific needs is now more than just a strategic choice; it is necessary. The push for social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic has solidified the trend of online shopping, and offering tailored recommendations has proven to be a highly effective approach for e-commerce sites (Wang et al., 2021). With AI technologies such as facial recognition, queue detection, visitor counter, and activity visualizer, customer segmentation is even accessible at physical touchpoints (Klimek, 2020).

Customer segmentation with AI goes beyond demographic and geographic classifications and has many dimensions, including psychological and behavioral aspects (Mende et al., 2023). Machine learning algorithms identify specific emotions and requirements of customers and suggest relevant products or services accordingly. In this regard, experts indicate the usage of product reviews and customer feedback for more accurate segmentation, as individuals usually share their sentiments and experiences with the product or service in these channels (Reddy et al., 2023). Furthermore, as data flows in, AI systems dynamically adjust and optimize their segmentation tactics in real-time, ensuring that marketing efforts remain relevant and timely.

AI is also making strides in the field of education. When instructors think of testing students' knowledge, exams and tests are the main factors for them to analyze. This aspect can change as AI tools can be used to analyze students' educational data to assist teachers in creating personalized learning plans (Kumar, 2021). For example, Brightspace Insights by D2L can analyze data from online sources, publishers, and learning apps to come up with a student's learning behavior. Brightspace Insights provides teachers with information for them to decide

how to teach, and it predicts the learner's current issues, allowing teachers to address the problem right away (Loeffler, 2018). Similarly, Georgia State University introduced an AI chatbot, Pounce, that reduced "summer melt" (i.e., students enrolled in spring dropping out of college in fall) by 22%. Using conversational AI technology, the chatbot was able to guide students in getting their queries answered in a timely and relevant manner, thereby helping them stay in college (Ravipati, 2017).

Customization and tailored products can have varying goals across different industries. While the financial industry aims to offer services tailored to diverse financial needs, the music industry focuses on emotions and interests. Spotify is a famous example of perfectly performing segmentation and personalization. "Hyper-personalization" in Spotify keeps users interested by continually offering new music, and increasing user activity on Spotify amplifies the AI's proficiency in delivering recommendations (Cohen, 2022). Not just customers but artists take advantage of the available data to understand who is listening to their tracks to determine prospective engagement, release methods, or even future career paths (PUSH.fm, 2023). Another interesting example is the houseplant brand "The Sill," which categorizes customers based on their lifestyles. They offer a pet-friendly subscription for animal owners and an easy-care option for busy individuals (Davey, 2023).

A notable perspective in customer segmentation and personalization is the mutual interest of companies and customers alike in understanding consumer profiles (Chamorro-Premuzic, 2023). The capabilities of AI extend beyond the modulation of consumer behaviors; instead, they uncover the deeper layers of consumer identity, which can also be interesting information for individuals. In this context, AI offers a unique chance to boost self-understanding and allows consumers to become not just smarter shoppers but also people with a better sense of themselves (Aw et al., 2022). For example, using response language models, chatbots can be programmed such that they can predict a consumer's personality during an interaction (Fan et al., 2023). This allows a chatbot to tailor its personality to match the consumer's, resulting in increased consumer engagement with the firm (Mende et al., 2023).

Overall, the utilization of AI-driven marketing tools offers a comprehensive approach for marketers to achieve various objectives. These tools enable the setting of precise goals, the gathering and analysis of relevant data, the selection of suitable AI methodologies for data evaluation, and the training of AI models using historical data. Additionally, they can also refine data attributes to improve the model's forecasting capability, perform statistical evaluations to confirm precision and dependability, transform data into visual representations such as charts and dashboards, and continuously refine AI models to adapt to evolving data (Analytics Vidhya, 2023a). Furthermore, marketing platforms such as HubSpot and Salesforce Einstein use AI to develop customer personas to understand the preferences, motivations, and pain points of different clusters of customers (Baker, 2023). This understanding is not limited to current customers; it encompasses leads and potential customers. AI tools score each lead based on engagement levels and behavioral patterns, then target them with tailored marketing campaigns (Nicole, 2023). For instance, financial institutions utilize machine learning engines to analyze transaction histories, account balances, and credit scores to introduce new services or offer more personalized investment consultations. Considering the importance of these insights, the following proposition is offered:

Proposition 1a. : AI-generated insights can enhance the prediction of customer purchasing behaviors across various channels and touchpoints, thereby significantly influencing product development within competitive market landscapes.

Although AI-driven segmentation offers businesses a powerful tool for understanding their customers' needs and preferences more accurately, it has potential risks and challenges. Mis-segmentation, where inaccurate data or flawed algorithms misclassify customers, can lead to misdirected marketing efforts and potentially alienating consumers. For example, in the healthcare system, if the data fed into the AI system is

flawed or incorrect, the AI's clinical recommendations can also be off the mark, leading to inappropriate treatment suggestions (Kristiansen et al., 2022). There is also the problem of maintaining a balance between personalization and inclusiveness so that marketing communications do not mistakenly reject potential buyers outside of the established groups. Instagram algorithms are known for creating a bubble that becomes so tailored to an individual's preferences that they inadvertently isolate the user from diverse content and perspectives (Bradley, 2016). Above all, balancing technological and human service delivery is crucial for brands, especially accommodating customers who prefer personal interactions, such as vulnerable demographics like the elderly or those with limited digital skills (Dwivedi et al., 2021). These preliminary insights set the stage for further investigation. Hence, in the case of AI-driven customer insights, we propose the following:

Proposition 1b. : The constraints inherent in AI technologies can substantially diminish their capacity to provide actionable customer insights, potentially leading to diminished effectiveness in decision-making processes.

2.5.1.2. Theme 2: Measuring marketing performance. Analytical marketing capabilities empower organizations with a sophisticated approach to measuring marketing performance. Employing AI in marketing initiatives yields a wealth of data, which remains valuable beyond post-campaign execution or algorithm-driven advertising. This data, rich in potential insights, can be instrumental in evaluating performance and engendering insightful analyses concerning campaign outcomes for informed decision-making.

Natural language processing, linking similar products based on consumer research, semantic understanding, and relevance instead of optimization, continues to drive the features of an AI-powered offering. Furthermore, it is possible to apply these aspects to content creation. For instance, AI enables the development of content-focused advertising, as seen in the case of McCann's AI tool, wherein the tool aids the creative team in scripting and filming commercials that resonate closely with the intended audiences (McEleny, 2016). Tools such as Grammarly and Quillbot can predict what the user wants to say and give recommendations to make the content concise and relevant. There are some areas where AI is better than humans in content marketing tasks, such as writing e-mail subject lines and suggesting keywords. As a result, companies can design their digital marketing strategies more efficiently by using AI, which can result in superior marketing performance (Kumar, 2021).

Regarding supervision and performance measurement, various AI tools are accessible to marketers. To evaluate the effectiveness of various advertising efforts, AI algorithms examine click-through rates, conversion rates, and consumer engagement levels. Marketers will then decide which campaigns impact the audience and which require performance optimization.

This discussion on measuring marketing performance is anchored in the analytical marketing capabilities and is explored through two sub-themes: (a) AI-powered analytics tools and (b) real-time performance tracking. AI-powered analytics tools not only enable companies to execute campaigns but also help them analyze the outcomes and anticipate future market trends. Beyond that, real-time performance monitoring highlights AI's dynamism and rapidness in marketing performance evaluation.

AI-powered analytics tools.

AI data analysis is the application of AI techniques and algorithms on large data to interpret and gain a deeper understanding of the performance and to have data-driven decision-making (Analytics Vidhya, 2023a). Over 40% of marketers have not only seen an uptick in the number of campaigns they managed from 2021 to 2022 but also have witnessed a surge in their campaign successes, underscoring the impact of AI-powered analysis (Decker, 2023).

AI analytics combine many aspects of AI to provide a modern data

experience using four key components: natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, neural networks, and deep learning (Arora, 2023; De Bruyn et al., 2020). NLP allows machines to process and interpret human language, simplifying text data analysis and the extraction of customer sentiment and important themes. Machine learning utilizes algorithms to analyze data and predict outcomes without being explicitly programmed, aiding in identifying patterns like fraud. Neural networks, inspired by human brain activity, are linked nodes that analyze data and are used in applications such as image and speech recognition. Finally, deep learning, a subset of neural networks, specializes in making exact predictions by training models on large amounts of data and is helpful in various AI applications, including handling unstructured data in AI analytics (Shetty et al., 2020).

AI-powered tools are varied and can be used for different purposes, from analyzing website traffic and social media engagement to assessing consumer behavior and estimating sales trends (Friedman, 2023). They can be categorized in various ways (e.g., copywriting, editing, digital marketing, and automation categories), each tailored to fulfill specific objectives within the marketing landscape. Jasper, Writer, and Surfer SEO are some of the tools used to accelerate and automate content writing and enhance the copywriting process by including characteristics that appeal to target audiences. For example, Surfer SEO focuses on elevating web page content quality to achieve higher rankings on search engine result pages by analyzing and comparing content with top-ranking pages and providing recommendations for SEO optimization (Matošević et al., 2021). Also, for digital marketing processes, Seventh Sense uses behavior profiling to identify optimal email campaign timing for each contact, and Optimove provides a customer data platform with insights into customer behavior and campaign performance.

Marketing practitioners also emphasize utilizing an integrated marketing analytics platform to have a centralized data flow, improve data accuracy, and create a holistic overview of the marketing ecosystem. One premier example is Adobe Analytics solution, which provides marketers with real-time information and in-depth segmentation across several marketing channels. This platform has customers among leaders of industries, and nine of the top 10 U.S. brands rely on it (Cohan, 2023; Forbes Technology Council, 2023). It aids in comprehending the efficacy of marketing techniques in boosting traffic and revenue. Ad hoc analysis, attribution modeling, audience targeting, customer journey mapping, and other functions are available through the platform (Analytics Vidhya, 2023b). Another key player is Marketo, now a part of the Adobe family. Marketo stands out for its robust marketing automation capabilities, which AI significantly enhances. It specializes in lead management, nurturing, and scoring, making it a vital tool for B2B marketing professionals.

These examples show the diverse and transformative impact of AI-powered analytics tools across various aspects of the marketing domain. Moving forward, smart use of AI-powered technologies will be critical in navigating market complexities, adjusting to changing customer behaviors, and guaranteeing long-term corporate growth in the increasingly digitized world.

Real-time performance tracking.

In the fast-paced, evolving industry landscape, firms must grasp current customer needs and sentiments (Zaki et al., 2021). Leveraging advanced AI and analytics tools, companies can instantly capture and analyze customer feedback, allowing them to adjust their products, services, or marketing strategies immediately. This level of responsiveness not only maintains business visibility among target audiences but also fosters enhanced trust and loyalty.

Real-time performance tracking using AI involves several key phases. Real-time performance tracking via AI consists of collecting, processing, enriching, and transforming raw data from various sources into valuable insights (Bonderud, 2023). AI engines enhance this data to formulate detailed user profiles. In the monitoring phase, AI aids in data visualization and instant report generation, with a marketing dashboard

displaying data through key performance indicators (KPIs) (Mattison, 2023). For example, Google Analytics dashboards provide a full perspective of website performance and display real-time data on user engagement, traffic sources, user demographics, and other metrics necessary for making informed marketing decisions (Sussman, 2020).

In the decision-making phase, AI helps to set predefined rules or algorithms based on organizational objectives and operational needs, and these algorithms will then trigger particular actions accordingly. For example, assume a customer frequently browses a specific product category from Amazon, such as electronics, but does not make a purchase; Amazon's AI system, which has predefined rules, recognizes this pattern and immediately triggers an action to send an optimized message to the customer with a special discount on electronics products (Bhattacharya, 2019). This action, informed by real-time data and executed by AI, tries to benefit from an opportunity (potential customer interest) and improve performance (increase sales) by providing the customer with a timely and relevant incentive.

Besides gathering data from customers' actions through various touchpoints, AI can analyze sentiment in real time to generate market intelligence on consumers' emotions and brand perceptions (Rambocas & Pacheco, 2018). Using machine learning engines, marketers observe texts, grammatical structures, and emoji usage to predict how the user feels and adjust their marketing initiatives accordingly (Ma et al., 2018). One of the established uses of machine learning for sentiment analysis is in the hospitality and tourism industry, where there is a need to understand and respond to customer feedback in real time (Mehraliyev et al., 2021). For example, Tripadvisor's Live Sentiment Dashboard provides daily actionable intelligence by analyzing data from 50 tourism touchpoints, including real-time conversations on platforms like Tripadvisor (Tripadvisor, 2021). This dashboard evaluates sentiment towards destinations and travel, enabling other companies to gauge their popularity compared to competitors and adjust marketing strategies accordingly.

In sum, the AI-enhanced analytical tools empower companies to make informed decisions for future strategies and operations, guided by the patterns and trends from the past (The Upwork Team, 2023). By examining consumer habits, purchasing trends, and engagement indicators, AI-enhanced analytical tool offers a more complex analysis of marketing effectiveness, allowing marketers to adjust their campaigns to fit the requirements and preferences of individual customers. By staying attuned to real-time customer needs and sentiments, firms can cultivate better customer relationships. This, in turn, elevates customer satisfaction and carves a competitive edge in the marketplace. Similarly, AI-enhanced analytical tool can analyze real-time data, detecting risks like fraud or breaches, enabling proactive measures to minimize losses. Hence, enabling companies to forecast future risks, implement preventive strategies, and enhance resilience and security. These observations serve as the foundation for further inquiry, and it is thus proposed that:

Proposition 2a. : The implementation of AI, including AI-powered analytics tools and real-time performance tracking, can have both short-term (e.g., optimize operations, insight generation, cost reduction) and long-term (e.g., enhanced predictive capabilities, innovation acceleration, risk mitigation) effects on marketing performance metrics.

Even though AI is powerful, it can't independently and consistently organize and manage successful marketing campaigns for a diverse consumer base, necessitating oversight and supervision (Geyser, 2023). While understanding customer future behavior and real-time performance tracking have become essential for supporting rapid choice-making and improving user experience, they are not without obstacles. Firstly, managing massive amounts of real-time data can be challenging, possibly leading to data overload, and hampering the extraction of relevant insights using AI tools (MarketScape, 2023). The next challenge is data privacy and security, especially in an era when data breaches are not uncommon, which mandates robust cybersecurity

processes to preserve information. Furthermore, with organizational growth, the quality and reliability of real-time data, integration of data from diverse sources, and system scalability emerge as crucial considerations. These insights call for an exploration to inform the future endeavors, therefore, we propose that:

Proposition 2b. : The constraints inherent in AI technologies can substantially diminish their ability to measure marketing performance, potentially leading to diminished accuracy and reliability of marketing performance measurement processes.

2.5.2. Technological marketing capabilities

Technological marketing capabilities center on integrating and applying AI technologies to enhance marketing efforts while also addressing the ethical concerns they raise. This capability is studied through the following themes: automated marketing strategies and ethical implications. Automated marketing strategies highlight the role of AI technologies in automating and enhancing marketing processes like customer services and ad placements (Manis & Madhavaram, 2023). Key elements of AI marketing automation encompass programmatic advertising, chatbots, and virtual assistants (Chen et al., 2021; Ciuchita et al., 2023). These components uncover a landscape where technology seamlessly merges with marketing, leading to more efficient, targeted, and better customer service (Gkikas & Theodoridis, 2022). Technological marketing capabilities also prompt ethical considerations, emphasizing the importance of safeguarding data privacy and security to uphold the integrity and confidentiality of information (Stahl & Wright, 2018). Similarly, the theme addresses algorithmic bias and discrimination, highlighting how algorithms can unintentionally reinforce prejudices, leading to unfair or even harmful decisions toward certain groups (Ferrer et al., 2021).

2.5.2.1. Theme 3: Automated marketing strategies. Technological marketing capabilities set the stage for optimizing and simplifying the execution of demanding marketing tasks while also personalizing customer communication, optimizing marketing budgets, and ensuring accurate targeting (De Bruyn et al., 2020). This automation not only speeds up the nurturing of high-quality, sales-ready leads but also frees up time for strategic, high-value work (Järvinen & Taiminen, 2016).

While the exact functionalities vary between solutions, marketing automation systems can help organizations with various approaches. For example, Oracle offers a marketing automation solution called "Oracle Eloqua," which provides comprehensive marketing automation tools for B2B marketers. The platform allows businesses to plan and execute campaigns, nurture leads, and measure and analyze marketing performance. Features include programmatic advertising, campaign management, lead scoring, segmentation, and integration with CRM systems (Allen, 2019; Olenski, 2022).

Two critical components of marketing automation—namely (a) programmatic advertising and (b) utilization of chatbots and virtual assistants, will be investigated in this theme. As part of the technological marketing capabilities, these components reveal a landscape where technology and marketing intertwine to create more efficient, targeted, and user-friendly customer experiences.

Programmatic advertising.

Programmatic advertising (PA) has emerged as a transformative shift in media buying over the past decade (Stevens et al., 2016). This technology has witnessed a surge in its share of total online advertising. This rise has paralleled advances in cost-effective and efficient techniques for online consumer tracking and targeting (Cooper et al., 2023). Anticipated to ascend to \$558 million in 2023, global programmatic advertising expenditure is on a notable upward trajectory, marking a 13.1% increase from 2022 and nearly doubling the figures recorded in 2019 (Statista, 2023a). Global programmatic budgets will rise by over \$300 billion within the next four years (Davis, 2023).

The core elements of programmatic advertising involve advertisers,

publishers, demand-side platforms (DSPs), and data management platforms (DMPs) to manage ad inventory and campaigns (Chen et al., 2019; Kiran & Arumugam, 2020; Riley, 2023). Advertisers market their products or services by reaching specific audiences via digital adverts. They manage their ad campaigns and buy ad inventory using DSPs (Kiran & Arumugam, 2020). DSPs are central to AI-powered programmatic purchasing. Based on algorithms targeting specific demographic groups, DSPs allow marketers to choose which impressions to buy and determine how much to bid on them. Publishers are website owners or managers who offer locations for marketers to show advertising materials on their websites to monetize their content (Riley, 2023). Next are DMPs, which create detailed user profiles using machine learning algorithms by collecting data across multiple platforms and transforming high-dimensional data into numerous “tags,” allowing for precise and flexible user targeting (Duan & Yang, 2018). When a user visits a publisher’s website, DMPs share the user’s details and the accessible ad space. The space is then auctioned off to the advertisers via DSPs. The advertiser with the highest bid can display their ad to the user. This automated process guarantees that advertising is shown to the most appropriate audiences, boosting the probability of engagement and conversion.

Programmatic advertising has diversified substantially, reaching the target consumers across numerous digital channels. These channels include display and video ads; programmatic TV advertising, which enables advertisers to detect competitor ad placements and strategically schedule their own; and digital out-of-home (DOOH), which presents dynamic ads in public spaces with real-time data adaptability (Guitart et al., 2020; Riley, 2023). Advertisers typically use a combination of these channels to create a cohesive narrative, ensuring that messages are not only seen but also contextually relevant and engaging to the audience across multiple touchpoints.

A successful example is *The Economist*, which has utilized subscriber data to curate tailored content for its “intellectually curious” audience. *The Economist* effectively targeted programmatic ad buying, presenting ads in real-time based on web page context and viewer profiles. These ads led users to relevant articles with subscription offers. With a £ 1.2 million media budget, the campaign attracted 650,000 new prospects and prompted 3.6 million actions post-ad viewing (Keane, 2023). However, due to the complexity and quick growth of PA technologies, marketers must engage in continual learning and adaptation to prevent obsolescence and guarantee that their tactics are optimal for the current digital ecosystem. While PA is a robust tool for modern digital marketing, it also needs careful maneuvering to avoid potential hazards and fit with both ethical issues and corporate objectives.

Chatbots and virtual assistants (generative tools).

The current technologically advanced era demands a heightened understanding of the needs and demands of customers, particularly in a progressively competitive marketplace. Intelligent agent technologies fundamentally alter frontline service interactions and stand out as a primary means to achieve this objective (Kumar et al., 2016; Robinson et al., 2020). Chatbots are AI engines designed to engage in sequential dialogues to reach a specific outcome, serve as facilitators for humans (Illescas-Manzano et al., 2021).

It was not until the mid-2010s that chatbots began to gain notable prominence in people’s lives. For example, Capital One’s Eno and Bank of America’s Erica entered the banking sector as AI-powered virtual banking assistants, offering mobile phone users assistance in handling their queries and financial matters. In 2016, Facebook opened its platform to chatbots, allowing businesses and developers access to its large user base (Yadron & Kiss, 2016). This shift not only propelled chatbots into mainstream consumer technologies but also provided businesses with a new option to interact with clients familiarly and comfortably. Furthermore, the advent and adoption of intelligent assistants such as Amazon’s Alexa, Google Assistant, and Apple’s Siri aided in integrating conversational AI into daily life. These virtual assistants not only increased people’s familiarity and comfort when conversing with

computers but also broadened the applications and use cases for chatbot technology (Chkroun & Azaria, 2021).

Chatbots are agile and powerful tools for generating leads and facilitating two-way communication that boosts company sales (Illescas-Manzano et al., 2021). With the advancement in technology, chatbots are being programmed such that their ability to recognize, simulate, and react to emotions appropriately, as humans do, is improving (Adamopoulou & Moussiades, 2020), leading to more engaging customer experiences (Tsai et al., 2021). For example, Woebot is an encrypted emotional chatbot that provides mental healthcare (i.e., acts as a trusted companion), particularly useful for reducing anxiety and depression. These encrypted emotional chatbots have practical implications for aging customers who require more enhanced and personalized engagements (Iancu & Iancu, 2023).

In today’s consumer landscape, there is a growing demand for seamless and immediate experiences (Ostrom et al., 2021). AI chatbots and virtual assistants are well-suited to meet this expectation. Leveraging vast amounts of data, chatbots can foster a relationship between customers and the firm by offering speed, convenience, personalization, and seamlessness (Kumar et al., 2019)—benefits that align with the expectations of today’s digitally connected consumers (Fotheringham & Wiles, 2023). For marketers, AI chatbots offer an economically efficient method to expand their reach and seamlessly manage customer interactions across various platforms (Kshetri et al., 2023). Successful chatbot implementation enables businesses to expand their customer service capabilities, supporting growth without additional training and hiring expenses (Iles, 2020).

While chatbots in marketing services help provide simple, rapidly received information, respondents are also concerned about chatbots providing incorrect and misleading information (Arsenijevic & Jovic, 2019). Moreover, there is a growing interest in designing multi-chatbot systems where each chatbot acts as a product/domain-specific adviser. In this regard, it is highlighted that a multi-chatbot interface might induce user confusion and unfamiliarity, which can decrease trust in digital commerce platforms (Tan & Liew, 2022). To address these challenges, businesses need to focus on enhancing chatbot technology to make it more human-like, empathetic, and transparent in its interactions with consumers (Kshetri et al., 2023; Tran et al., 2021). These digital assistants are anticipated to expand as technology advances, necessitating ongoing research and understanding of their capabilities and implications. Businesses and researchers must find a balance between using this technology and maintaining the human element, which is critical for meaningful consumer connections in the digital communication era.

Overall, as an automated, big-data system, Programmatic Advertising (PA) empowers organizations to bid for the chance to showcase personalized advertising in the most pertinent locations and times for the targeted audience (Samuel et al., 2021). This type of advertising uses web users’ digital footprints and presents relevant ads to them (Benady, 2015). Employing sophisticated software and algorithms to acquire ad impressions through ad exchanges, PA ensures that not only brand’s message reaches its precise audience at the opportune moment (Riley, 2023), but also allows the brands to have access to many publisher sites simultaneously. Similarly, digital assistants such as chatbots use natural language processing to recognize patterns from data using techniques such as facial recognition, speech recognition, and text mining to simulate human conversation, improving user engagement and offering prompt support (Fan et al., 2023; Kshetri et al., 2023). These initial observations pave the way for a deeper investigation. Hence, we propose:

Proposition 3a. : Implementing automated marketing strategies like programmatic advertising, and chatbots/virtual assistants can lead to a substantial increase in long-term loyalty and improved customer retention for companies.

Even though AI chatbots and virtual assistants have clear, well-

defined customer and firm benefits, there exist multiple drawbacks and challenges associated with their widespread adoption. Interactions with chatbots can influence consumers' expectations, potentially affecting how they anticipate future interactions with human agents. For example, a chatbot's quick response may lead consumers to expect similar response times from human agents. This is crucial since chatbots often work alongside, not in place of, human agents. Similarly, consumers may perceive AI chatbots as inauthentic (Liu-Thompkins et al., 2022). This perception can arise because of automated information, which may appear robotic, given chatbots' ongoing challenges in comprehending and showing empathy for the complex emotional and personal aspects (Crollic et al., 2022). Similarly, PA has grown rapidly and is well accepted, there have also been cautionary tales of costly blunders (Samuel et al., 2021) and ineffective advertisement campaigns (Bakpayev et al., 2022). Some campaigns have received backlash owing to incorrect ad placements or mismatched targeting, underscoring the significance of a well-planned approach. Among the companies that faced problems was JP Morgan Chase, which removed its advertisements from YouTube after they were mistakenly displayed alongside unsuitable and extremist content because of PA errors (Maheshwari, 2017). Furthermore, Adidas suspended its advertising on YouTube after its ads were shown alongside exploitative videos of children (Goodfellow, 2017). Based on above discussion and insights, we present the following proposition:

Proposition 3b. : Incorporating AI into traditional marketing strategies can pose considerable challenges, potentially requiring innovative solutions to overcome hurdles and ensuring successful implementation.

2.5.2.2. Theme 4: Ethical implications. In the evolving digital landscape, AI-driven technologies have penetrated multiple industry sectors, from healthcare and finance to education, criminal justice, and customer service, to name a few (Ettari et al., 2022; Mende et al., 2023; Mishra, 2023; Noble & Mende, 2023; Svetlova, 2022; Wirtz et al., 2022). This research has consistently demonstrated a connection between AI and issues about ethics, justice, and privacy. AI's strong performance hinges on large datasets, advanced algorithms, and detailed machine-learning methods (ET Online, 2023). While this approach offers accuracy and automation, it also requires handling various data types. Each type presents potential ethical and privacy challenges, impacting not only individual users but the broader society (Wirtz et al., 2022).

Crucially, the ethical dimensions of AI transcend mere technological boundaries. They encapsulate broader sociological, psychological, and cultural implications. This necessitates a comprehensive, multi-disciplinary strategy, warranting both corporate and governmental intervention, to effectively comprehend and modulate them.

We delineate two primary focal areas. First, data privacy and security: In the AI landscape, data is akin to the fuel that drives the machinery; its purity and safety ensure the engine's optimal operation. Second, algorithmic bias and discrimination: Algorithms, when left unchecked, can unknowingly perpetuate prejudices, which can lead to decisions that are not only unfair but could also harm certain sections of the population. The objective is to highlight the array of ethical challenges within the AI realm through these subthemes while offering pragmatic insights, guidelines, and methods that could steer the ethical evolution and application of AI systems.

Data privacy and security.

The discourse on privacy and AI often centers on striking a balance between a "right to privacy" and the benefits that come from granting companies access to user data, such as improved service personalization, augmented corporate profitability, and the establishment of a regulatory framework conducive to optimal outcomes (Elliott & Soifer, 2022). Some experts emphasize gaining customer trust, while others emphasize building clear frameworks and using more secure algorithm developments (Forbes Technology Council, 2023). For instance, it is argued that when customers understand the benefits of AI applications,

they will actively share personal information in exchange for receiving rewards and incentives (Wang et al., 2021). It is also suggested that regulators enhance supervision to increase consumer trust and protect privacy. In the healthcare sector, Larson et al. (2020) advocate that all organizations that access clinical data should act as "data stewards," with a duty of confidentiality to patients to protect their privacy and to the public to guarantee that data is freely accessible for the development of knowledge and tools to assist present and future patients.

AI systems amass vast amounts of data, and when such data is unlinked or not attributable to a specific individual, it may not directly infringe on that individual's privacy (Elliott & Soifer, 2022). Companies should harness this data by crafting algorithms that do not necessitate the identification of whom the data belongs to (World Economic Forum, 2022). This could be achieved through databases that employ anonymous identifiers, thwarting recognition or association with individuals or groups. For example, in the retail sector, AI systems can be engineered such that purchasing data does not directly correlate to individual customer profiles; instead, each set of purchasing habits is assigned an identifier. This allows the retailer to glean insights regarding product popularity without encroaching on customer privacy. Similarly, firms utilize anonymous surveys to garner feedback on their performance, often offering compensation to participants as an incentive.

Although using anonymous identifiers is a well-known and efficient way to maintain data privacy, there might be instances where they may pose risks and influence security interests. For example, suppose the anonymous identifier is associated with a set of purchasing behaviors that the AI considers high-risk (e.g., frequent purchases of high-value items); in that case, the identifier can be flagged as a high-risk customer. Such identifier can be later used to inform the credit service company that provides loans or credit to customers, and even though the initial data collection did not directly link purchasing habits to specific individuals when a customer applies for credit from the business, the AI may match their purchasing patterns with the anonymized high-risk profile. This can potentially influence the decision of the credit card company to deny credit or offer less favorable terms.

Moreover, knowing that there is a thin line between data privacy and artificial intelligence, there might be instances where using private information is inevitable, and there are numerous secure ways to use it non-invasively. Data encryptions and access controls are a way to prevent unauthorized access. For example, homomorphic encryption allows calculations on encrypted data without decrypting it (Ren et al., 2021). Scientists also suggest on-device processing and federated learning to process data directly on the user's device and train computer models on devices without moving the actual data around (Li et al., 2020). Data retention policies also ensure that data is stored only for the required duration and is securely deleted after that period.

Another pressing matter is the accountability aspect of data privacy, which extends beyond mere compliance with data protection laws. Accountability for companies means not only implementing systems that protect data but also being responsible for decisions made based on that data. With AI's role in data collection and analysis, the traditional clarity of human responsibility becomes blurred, necessitating strategies for transparency and explainability in AI systems (Collina et al., 2023). This is critical in ensuring a clear line of accountability in AI-informed processes. In this regard, Wirtz et al. (2023) introduce the concept of corporate digital responsibility (CDR) and emphasize tactics and procedures that businesses can employ to establish a robust CDR culture (Kunz & Wirtz, 2023). An example of the accountability challenges is Meta's recent \$51 million settlement in a class-action lawsuit in Canada as a result of AI-driven marketing strategies (CBC/Radio Canada, 2024). In this instance, Facebook has used users' images in their AI-generated ad without explicit user consent, which underscores the crucial need for responsible data practices and the potential repercussions of failing to adhere to these standards.

Algorithmic bias and discrimination.

In the realm of machine learning algorithms and data interpretation,

the issue of algorithmic bias and discrimination stands out as a well-acknowledged yet critical concern. Algorithmic bias refers to persistent, systematic errors in computer systems that result in unequal outcomes, such as favoring a particular user group. This bias can stem from several sources, including skewed training data, erroneous model designs, or biased decision-making processes (Zewe, 2022). For example, Buolamwini and Gebru (2018) found that commercial AI systems from companies like IBM, Microsoft, and Face++ had significant issues with gender classification bias. The systems were tested on a dataset of faces, and the findings revealed that the facial recognition software did well in classifying the gender of people with lighter skin tones but suffered a lot with those with darker skin tones, especially women.

Furthermore, AI harbors a more profound, more complex impact on society. For instance, biased algorithms in financial technologies could yield unfair loan approval rates across diverse racial or socio-economic groups. Likewise, with facial recognition technologies, biases against certain ethnicities or genders may result in misidentification and unjust treatment. In this vein, Ledford (2019) noted that an algorithm prevalent in the U.S. aimed at predicting patient referrals to programs for enhanced care demonstrated a lesser likelihood to recommend Black individuals compared to White ones.

In the context of marketing, recommendation algorithms on e-commerce platforms can reinforce and magnify existing social and economic imbalances by recommending lower-quality or cheaper products to lower-income individuals. Similarly, advertising algorithms may exclude users from an ad due to their interests in specific ethnic groups. Addressing biases, showcased in the earlier examples and underscored in a report by the *New York Times* on Facebook's allowance for advertisers to exclude users based on "ethnic affinity" in housing-related ads—a practice in violation of the U.S. Fair Housing Act—is more than a technical challenge; it is an ethical imperative calling for a comprehensive strategy (Benner et al., 2019).

The above discussion illustrates that despite the considerable attention and various approaches from authors and practitioners, the journey toward mitigating biases and discriminations in AI is still a long one. There is a long path ahead to reach a satisfactory point where we can confidently affirm that biases and discriminations have been adequately minimized.

Beyond data privacy and algorithmic bias, several additional risks associated with AI could impact organizations, consumers, and society. These include challenges in the governance and learning capabilities of AI systems, concerns about the quality of data feeding into AI/ML systems, and the susceptibility to various AI/ML attacks, such as data poisoning and adversarial inputs (Mudgal et al., 2023). Moreover, issues in effectively testing AI systems and ensuring transparency also present significant risks, necessitating careful management and oversight. To address these issues, the National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) released the AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0) in January 2023. This framework, developed collaboratively with private and public sectors, aims to manage risks in AI, focusing on trustworthiness in AI design, development, and evaluation. It was created through a comprehensive, transparent process involving public feedback and workshops (NIST, 2023). Compliance with such regulations is crucial, as it ensures that AI systems are developed and deployed with a focus on trustworthiness, safety, and transparency. It can also help mitigate potential harm to consumers and society, thereby enhancing the credibility and acceptance of AI technologies.

Overall, in the light of recent developments, a critical examination of the ethical implications of AI-driven marketing is a vital concern. The challenges with AI are numerous, ranging from the risk of biased algorithms causing discrimination to concern about data breaches, hidden data selling, and profound ethical dilemmas like forced data sharing and losing the human touch (Breidbach & Maglio, 2020; Wirtz et al., 2022). For businesses in this complex landscape, a clear, ethics-focused plan is essential to protect stakeholders' interests. These concerns underscore that competent privacy and data management procedures extend

beyond alleviating customers' anxieties and concerns; they are intrinsic to the company's core organizational principles, business operations, and security management. Companies that use AI in any aspect of their business, whether upfront or in the backend, should address these concerns contextually. It can start with transparent communication and security protocols and move further to regular employee training and developing new products, services, or processes that integrate privacy considerations from the outset. This examination lays the groundwork for advancing our understanding further, it is thus proposed that:

Proposition 4a. : The development of AI frameworks that emphasize fairness, transparency, and responsible practices can help firms to better govern the application of AI in marketing.

Amidst the ongoing discourse surrounding bias, it is crucial to recognize that bias is inevitable in AI as these machines and technologies are built by humans, who have their own perceptions and biases of events (DataForce, 2022). Transparent algorithm design can help develop both explainable and transparent algorithms for stakeholders. The first step in reducing these biases is ensuring inclusive and representative data collection and processing. Going forward, the onus should be on minimizing these misunderstandings to build systems that can work without discrimination. In the rapidly evolving field of AI, it is suggested that bias research be at the forefront to help establish processes that consciously reduce bias. This involves comparing the outputs of algorithms with human decisions and employing "explainability techniques" to understand the differences in decision-making processes (Dallanocce, 2022). Exploring the potential of human-machine collaboration to reduce bias is also advised, including implementing "human-in-the-loop" processes (Wolfewicz, 2022). Finally, increasing investments in bias research, providing more data, and diversifying the AI community are other vital steps to position and address these challenges strategically. These insights set the stage for further investigation. Therefore, it is proposed:

Proposition 4b. : Ethical considerations related to data privacy, security, and algorithmic bias in AI-driven marketing practices can significantly enhance the trust levels of both consumers and employees.

2.5.3. Strategic efficiency capabilities

Strategic efficiency capabilities focus on strategically deploying AI to optimize marketing operations and enhance customer experiences beyond expectations (Campbell et al., 2020). It involves balancing the practical and the innovative potential of AI to revolutionize customer experience and satisfaction through personalized and responsive experiences. This capability is studied through two themes: enhancing customer experiences and growth opportunities with AI implementation. Enhancing customer experiences relates to real-time customer assistance as a form of support beyond chatbots, available at any point in the customer journey and capable of addressing and resolving problems immediately (Manis & Madhavaram, 2023). Furthermore, we explore customer experiences beyond the physical environment, leveraging AI in conjunction with extended realities to create immersive and interactive experiences in various sectors, thereby reshaping customer interactions and journeys in the digital world (Reiners et al., 2021). In the case of growth opportunities, we discuss a spectrum of challenges and opportunities in assessing the benefits of early adoption of AI in marketing and its long-term advantages.

2.5.3.1. Theme 5: Enhancing customer experiences. When studying strategic efficiency capabilities, AI emerges as a compelling tool for businesses to streamline operations while significantly improving the way customers interact with brands. AI's role in providing real-time customer assistance marks a significant advancement in enhancing customer experience. It offers individuals instant, on-the-spot assistance, ensuring their demands are handled effectively and promptly. It also provides a more in-depth understanding of customer assistance beyond

the basic application of chatbots and virtual assistants.

AI also looks at the individual's behaviors as one browses through websites and picks content that grants users a more exceptional experience based on previous interests (Kumar, 2021). In such a scenario, information on (a) customer-firm exchanges, (b) the typical consumer usage behaviors of goods and services, and (c) the typical contact format between firms and customers to ascertain the specifics of the firm offerings to pitch to the right customers. For instance, Google Maps uses AI to provide optimal routes through algorithms and provide road information to users. Some other examples of AI solutions geared towards personalization include customizing website content (e.g., Wix), price (e.g., Perfect Price – for dynamic pricing), and customer interactions (e.g., Samsung SmartThings ecosystem).

Beyond the physical environment, AI's true potential can be unlocked with extended realities. Through investigation of AI's capabilities within extended realities, we look into the future of a customer's journey, envisioning a landscape where every interaction is not only personalized but also deeply immersive, transforming the way brands connect with their consumers. Hence, in the fifth theme, we discuss enhancing customer experience as a strategic efficiency capability, examining its potential to redefine both our physical and virtual environments.

Extended realities, the metaverse, and spatial computing.

The past decade has seen a significant increase in academic research and practical applications of extended realities in the business and retail sectors (Cipresso et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023). Large companies such as Coca-Cola, McDonald's, IKEA, and General Electric are implementing extended reality (XR) in their marketing initiatives (Gilliland, 2021). Additionally, the XR market (i.e., AR, VR, and Metaverse) is projected to grow to \$53.7 billion by 2027 (Statista, 2023b).

Three main branches of AI relevant to XR are computer vision, generative AI, and large language models (Jaehnic, 2023). Computer vision helps XR apps recognize and understand environmental elements and place virtual objects in the real world, allowing them to interact with that environment (Zewe, 2023). Generative AI generates media formats like photos, films, or 3D assets that can be later used in creating XR environments. Finally, yet significantly, large language models are utilized to analyze language prompts and return language replies to improve user interactions with non-human agents and characters in virtual worlds (Yang et al., 2022). This results in a more intuitive and natural user experience.

In an XR environment, AI algorithms examine user and environmental data to adjust the real-time XR experience (Barrera & Shah, 2023). AI-driven machine-learning algorithms can personalize the XR experience based on the user's actions, preferences, or past behavior (Noble & Mende, 2023; Yoo et al., 2023). For example, BMW uses Tango, Google's smartphone AR technology that lets users personalize and engage with a virtual BMW i3 or i8. The virtual car can be placed in the user's environment using computer vision, and the AI engine suggests car alterations depending on user interactions and preferences, improving the customer experience in real time.

The combination of AI and the XR has potential applications across several industries. For example, in the gaming industry, AI can create a more realistic and dynamic world. This technology can assist in crafting virtual worlds that closely mirror our physical environment, create avatars that look like humans and offer multilingual accessibility (Iliescu, 2023; Salazar, 2023; Yoo et al., 2023). In the retailing industry, retailers are employing AI in virtual storefronts to facilitate more immersive shopping experiences. Interactive displays and AI-powered chatbots provide additional product information and create engaging experiences as customers navigate the virtual storefront (Bonetti et al., 2023). Haomaiyi, a prominent online retailer in China, has developed a virtual fitting technology that provides every customer with an exclusive AI fashion consultant. This consultant dynamically matches customer information (e.g., sizes and previous purchases) and provides style advice

and a virtual trial experience. This AI-driven virtual reality experience has proven to convert 12.4% of fitting consumers into buyers and has led to approximately a 30% reduction in the return rate for certain brands (Yang et al., 2022).

Implementing AI within XR presents its unique set of obstacles, including technical and accessibility difficulties, as well as concerns about health and legal matters. Ensuring that AI-driven XR experiences are smooth, realistic, and glitch-free is a complex and resource-demanding task. Even if we assume that the technological problems are easy to solve, ensuring that AI-driven XR experiences are accessible and inclusive is a significant challenge in the current stage of these technologies. Important health implications such as eye strain, motion sickness, and potential psychological impacts can be expected due to constant exposure to XR (Daşdemir, 2023). Lastly, legal frameworks regarding data usage and user rights in AI-driven XR are still underdeveloped, which indicates further precautions on the part of companies that are developing such technologies (Karp, 2023).

As we move toward a future in which the digital and physical worlds become increasingly interconnected, a balanced approach to encourage innovation while protecting user experience, health, and rights will be critical in achieving corporate goals. Technologists, legislators, and industry leaders must collaborate constructively to develop an approach that optimizes advantages while reducing the risks and obstacles.

Real-time customer assistance.

Today's world demands immediate assistance and rapid solutions when it comes to enhancing customer journeys. Such assistance, facilitated by AI, not only increases customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty but also provides businesses with a better understanding of their consumers (Das et al., 2023). AI's role in providing real-time assistance can be seen in the case of voice assistants (Kumar, 2021). For instance, Amazon, Google, and Apple continue to work on advancing their AI devices. Amazon aims to allow for conversations with Alexa to last longer without having to repeat the wake word "Alexa" before every request. Google's Duplex on the Web enables Google Assistant to book appointments, make reservations, and even book car rentals using autofill. Apple plans to update Siri with voice-recognition ability to provide the user with customized recommendations.

There is a broad range of applications for AI-based real-time assistance. Cutting-edge AI-driven technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), deep learning (DL), cognitive computing (CC), and machine learning (ML) can help solve problems in real time (Behera et al., 2021). For example, AI-driven cognitive virtual assistants offer consistent, personalized, contextual, and instant responses to common inquiries. When more complex issues demand human intervention, they efficiently transfer them to customer service representatives. This transition ensures seamless, personalized, and contextual customer service around the clock. For example, the AI-driven customer support solutions powered by Instacart Storefront convert merchants' apps into helpful assistants, guiding and assisting customers throughout their in-store shopping journeys. This novel "AI In-Store" feature helps customers check stock availability, access detailed information about items on their shopping list, receive product recommendations, and avail themselves of in-store promotions and discounts (Rao & Zhang, 2021; Ryan, 2023). If a specified item is out of stock, the system alerts the consumer instantly, avoiding any difficulty after the purchase is placed.

A vital yet often overlooked use of AI in immediate support pertains to accessibility features such as image descriptions, voice navigation, and personalized content adjustments for all users, particularly those with disabilities (Vieira et al., 2022). The app "Seeing AI" is designed for individuals with visual impairments. It is capable of reading and providing descriptions for various types of documents and can recognize images, colors, and faces, offering insights into people's emotions. Google's Euphonia is an example that helps individuals with talking disabilities (Weitzman, 2023).

Despite these benefits, many challenges still exist. A significant concern is losing the personal touch of human interaction, which can be

crucial in building customer relationships (Sever, 2023). The absence of emotional intelligence, genuine empathy, and deep contextual knowledge in AI-based conversations is also a limitation in some scenarios where human touch is needed. For example, the AI assistant, Pi, while applicable for encouragement and support, lacks the emotional depth and complexity of human connection (Griffith, 2023). In addition, over-reliance on AI can lead to reduced human staffing, and it may get challenging when human intervention is urgently needed.

Above all, obtaining and keeping user trust is one of the most significant challenging issues for marketers (Danks, 2019; Troshani et al., 2021). AI systems are robust but not flawless; they can make mistakes, sometimes due to biases in the data they were trained on and sometimes due to unanticipated events. The inconsistent and unpredictable AI behavior can significantly damage consumers' faith in the system. This is especially important in sensitive scenarios like healthcare and finance, where mistakes can have serious outcomes. Furthermore, the opacity of some AI systems makes it impossible for consumers to understand how decisions or judgments were made, undermining confidence even further. Therefore, finding a balance between AI and human involvement emerges as a crucial priority for marketers, allowing them to harness the respective strengths of each to deliver highly effective customer service (Sever, 2023).

In sum, considering the increasing interest in the extended reality (XR), businesses begin taking the next logical steps to make these experiences more intelligent and tailored to individual users (Barrera & Shah, 2023). This is where AI becomes the perfect complement, with its capabilities to process vast amounts of data and learn from user interactions. Enhancing customer experience in extended realities involves leveraging AI in conjunction with augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and the metaverse to create immersive, interactive environments for customers. This combination provides users with sensory experiences that can include sight, sound, and even touch, making the digital interaction feel as real as the physical world. Intelligent reality (IR)—a fusion of AI and XR—has opened new avenues for innovation, allowing for more personalized and interactive user experiences. Even though AI and XR have different origins and objectives, their synergy strengthens the immersive and dynamic aspects and makes them more intelligent, responsive, and user-specific (Lampropoulos, 2023; Reiners et al., 2021). These observations are pivotal for a deeper investigation. Hence, we propose:

Proposition 5a. : AI can play a pivotal role in shaping seamless omnichannel customer experiences by crafting interactive and personalized customer interactions across diverse industries and platforms.

As AI-based real-time assistance can provide support available to customers at any point in the purchasing journey, it is capable of addressing and resolving problems within seconds. It involves a variety of features, among which are delivering instant feedback, individualized recommendations, and efficient problem-solving. AI's role in real-time customer assistance can also be seen in activities such as categorizing support tickets and emails, performing text and sentiment analysis, and facilitating multilingual support (Kleinings, 2023). Overall, the integration of AI, particularly through real-time customer assistance, empowers businesses to deliver superior service experiences that are personalized, immediate, reliable, and available round the clock, thereby significantly enhancing customer satisfaction levels (Behera et al., 2021; Das et al., 2023). This analysis serves as a foundation for further inquiry, and hence, we propose:

Proposition 5b. : The integration of AI, such as real-time customer assistance, can significantly increase customer satisfaction levels, potentially surpassing traditional customer interaction methods in terms of effectiveness and efficiency.

2.5.3.2. *Theme 6: Growth opportunities with AI implementation.* AI can augment or entirely supplant human capabilities within business

environments, introducing an array of opportunities. AI implementation offers businesses the potential to drive growth, innovation, and competitive advantage across various aspects of their operations, positioning them for long-term success in an increasingly digital and data-driven economy. Although AI as a strategic efficiency capability is necessary for businesses to improve operations and enhance customer experience, it is essential to acknowledge its costs and benefits. Due to the widespread availability and early adoption of rivals, AI does not offer a permanent competitive advantage. Moreover, machines can handle uncertain situations, but they also need defined goals and restrictions, which can be absent in some business contexts because of businesses' fluctuating internal and external factors. Under these circumstances, humans remain extremely important in situations requiring high ambiguity and human intuition.

Within the framework of strategic efficiency capabilities, in this theme, we will look into two key factors that influence how AI is used in competitive marketing environments, namely (a) early adoption benefits, which have several immediate and noticeable advantages to organizations and individuals, and (b) long-term advantages, which demand a more deliberate and strategic approach.

Early adoption benefits.

Companies worldwide have started to adopt AI by integrating it into their existing marketing systems and processes to get AI-driven insights that guide decision-making. The adoption rate is expected to grow at an annual rate of 37.3% from 2023 to 2030 (Haan, 2023). Since the adoption is still in its early stages, the process has been dynamic, with ongoing refinements based on feedback, outcomes, and shifting goals (Rascop, 2022). The practical advantages and widespread acceptance of AI technology were not as well-known a few years ago as they are now, and the market was filled with skepticism and cautious optimism (Bughin et al., 2017; Hagerup, 2023). Hesitancy towards AI adoption in those days was attributed to factors like confusion about its practical applications, a "wait and see" attitude, fear of the unknown, and concerns about the investment requirement for implementation (Puntoni et al., 2021).

Companies that adopt AI early on and use it to their advantage are already experiencing a competitive advantage. For example, companies like Google, Apple, and Microsoft were among the first to incorporate AI into their business process and are now reaping the benefits. Notably, Apple launched Siri in 2011, and Microsoft followed suit with Cortana in 2014 (Kanade, 2022; Sanchez, 2023). Tesla has led the way in incorporating AI into its cars, notably through its Autopilot system, which debuted its initial version in 2014 (Barry, 2021). Many prominent banks and financial organizations, like J.P. Morgan and Goldman Sachs, started to use AI for algorithmic trading, fraud detection, and customer support chatbots in the early stages.

In the marketing domain, Amazon was an early adopter of AI, employing it for product suggestions, shipping efficiency, and the Amazon Go retail concept (Harrigan, 2022). Netflix and Spotify have also been using AI for years to recommend shows, movies, and music to their users based on their viewing and listening habits. Starbucks was also an early adopter of AI for personalized marketing through its mobile app and uses AI to analyze customer preferences and purchase history to offer personalized offers. This underscores the importance of early adoption, not just technological tools and assets; essentially, any resource that companies manage to access before their competitors can confer a competitive advantage upon them. As the resource-based view (RBV) highlights, a firm's competitive advantage is based on valuable, rare, inimitable, and unique resources (Barney, 1991). When resources, such as technology, become imitable, securing early access becomes necessary.

Due to the extensive time and detailed procedures needed to develop and implement AI systems, being a follower may not be an optimal decision (Mahidhar & Davenport, 2018). Early adopters can scale quickly after the initial adoption phase, especially with their access to abundant data and knowledge engineering skills. Late adopters,

however, might find themselves in a never-ending race to catch up, where the gap between their abilities and those of the industry leaders grows wider with each technological breakthrough. Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) may be among the late adopters of AI-based marketing strategies due to budget constraints and limited access to advanced technology. Along with developing new skill sets to tackle the change management that comes with AI integration, the challenge goes beyond technology to include cultivating an organizational culture that is flexible to AI-driven transformations (Hau, 2023).

In conclusion, the route to AI adoption is complicated, requiring extensive research, strategic planning, and proactive execution. While AI adoption was first regarded with skepticism, the present environment emphasizes its role in driving business outcomes and creating industry norms. The message is clear: Proactive adoption and constant adaptation are not only helpful but also required for future success in the field of AI.

Long-term advantages.

In terms of long-term impact, research has advanced the notion that firms are likely to equip themselves better in delivering AI solutions that encompass all aspects of customer interaction with the firm instead of being deployed at only specific usage instances often deployed in the short run (Kumar et al., 2019). In this regard, research has identified that developed market firms' personalization approach is likely to focus on (a) strengthening their brand value, (b) incorporating human-machine interaction as a core feature, and (c) serving customers across varying profitability levels (rather than focus only on high-profit customers) to serve as the cornerstones of their marketing strategy (Kumar, 2021).

In the context of marketing, AI's role as a competitive advantage is significantly amplified by the underlying data it processes (Shelpuk, 2023). AI serves as the instrument that converts data into insightful knowledge, which could be used to improve a company's offerings (Fowler, 2020). This enhancement attracts more data and feedback, creating a self-reinforcing cycle where the product's value amplifies with an expanding user base. This evolving cycle not only strengthens a brand's market position but also establishes a formidable competitive barrier. (e.g., extensive quantities of data from both customers and business operations). Nevertheless, accessing such data necessitates having a product in the first place.

Besides data, talent' and trust are core assets in leveraging AI for a competitive edge (Gordon, 2019). In an AI-dominated environment, continuous learning becomes the basis of driving a competitive edge for enterprises (Kchaou, 2023). The growth of AI brings unanticipated competition, perhaps even from previously unrelated industries. Companies like Apple, Google, and Amazon, primarily renowned as technological companies, have entered the financial services market with offerings like Apple Card, Google Wallet, and Amazon Lending (Cross, 2022). This evolution underscores the need for marketing teams to be agile, adaptive, and continuously innovative. Marketing professionals must not only understand the new power structures shaped by AI but also actively engage in reshaping their marketing strategies to align with these emerging trends. The future of marketing will favor those organizations that can quickly adapt to AI-driven changes and embrace continuous learning (Manyika & Sneider, 2018).

Trust is the central pillar for successfully achieving a competitive edge, primarily because AI's efficacy relies on data sharing (Boehm et al., 2022). Without trust between the company and its customers, the data flow can be restricted, limiting the potential of AI-driven personalized and real-time solutions. Trust ensures that consumers are comfortable sharing their data and confident in its ethical and secure handling. This not only facilitates enhanced AI results but also brings brand loyalty and enduring customer ties (Bhalla, 2020). Consequently, companies that maintain high ethical standards and gain trust are likely to succeed, while those perceived as untrustworthy or unethical face significant repercussions.

Google exemplifies a company that successfully integrates AI into its services and assures its long-term success. With access to extensive data through various platforms like its search engine and YouTube, Google

harnesses the information to refine its algorithms and enhance user experience continually (Burr, 2023). This data-driven approach is bolstered by their commitment to attracting top-tier talent, which is evident in their innovative AI projects and a workforce comprising some of the best minds in engineering and AI research. Google effectively utilizes AI in its marketing efforts, particularly through Google Ads and Performance Max (Indacochea, 2021). This feature allows businesses to set campaign goals and provide creative assets. Then, it takes over crafting and executing highly effective ad campaigns across various Google platforms tailored to the advertisers' budgets.

Overall, despite the risks and difficulties, AI continues to develop and become a crucial game-changer across numerous industries (Pratt, 2023). Early adopters in the marketing realm are now reaping tangible benefits due to the advanced development and accessibility of AI tools, including generative AI tools and extensive language models like ChatGPT (Hagerup, 2023). Gartner (2023) predicts that by 2028, 50% of businesses will have AI-powered operational, demand, and other types of planning in place of time-consuming bottom-up forecasting techniques, as AI is expected to offer long-term benefits in improved decision-making abilities, cost savings, and operational efficiency. Companies that have been proactive in adopting AI have acquired a competitive advantage, while those that postpone or reject this inevitable transformation risk being left behind in an increasingly AI-driven future. In conclusion, securing a long-term advantage with AI hinges on adept data management, strategic application, and the trust firms foster with their audience. More than simply integrating AI techniques and algorithms is required to ensure a long-term advantage in the market. Hence, it is proposed that in future for businesses to remain ahead in the AI landscape, they must focus on continuous innovation flexibility and uphold ethical standards. More specifically, we propose:

Proposition 6a. : Implementing AI-driven marketing strategies can yield positive outcomes, including improved return on investment (ROI) and enhanced efficiency.

Attaining a long-term advantage has always been of interest to businesses (Kuncoro & Suriani, 2018). While short-term gains might be beneficial, a continuous competitive advantage can position a business as a market leader, ensuring long-term success. When adopted strategically, AI can offer businesses sustainable competitive advantages that are hard for competitors to replicate. By leveraging AI technologies effectively, businesses can achieve significant cost reductions across various aspects of their operations, contributing to improved profitability and long-term sustainability. For instance, implementing an AI-powered chatbot for customer inquiries carries potential advantages. The chatbot, being operational 24/7, can handle multiple queries concurrently, aiding human representatives, reducing wait times, and potentially enhancing customer satisfaction while curbing labor costs. Similarly, AI streamlines marketing tasks like optimizing campaigns, creating content, and supporting customers, cutting down on manual work and costs. This boosts efficiency, saving businesses money in the long run. This being the case, a deeper investigation will be pivotal for informing future endeavors, hence, we propose:

Proposition 6b. : Adopting AI-driven marketing strategies as opposed to traditional approaches can result in substantial cost reductions in the long-term vs. short-term.

3. General discussion

This study highlights the burgeoning and transformative role of AI in marketing, emphasizing its exponential growth and integration within the industry. Grounded in the framework of dynamic capability theory, we delve into the impact of AI on marketing processes, including decision-making, customer experience, operational efficiency, automation, marketing performance, and the growth opportunities with AI implementation AI's remarkable ability to enable organizations to

innovate and enhance operational facets is explored, with an emphasis on the importance of a strategic and deliberate approach to AI integration. Through the lens of dynamic capability theory, our analysis demonstrates how AI acts as a catalyst for firms to develop, adapt, and renew their capabilities in response to rapidly changing market environments.

Our discussion centers on the transformative impact of AI-driven marketing capabilities (Kumar, 2021), which we categorize into three main types: analytical, technological, and strategic efficiency capabilities. These categories illuminate the ways in which AI can revolutionize marketing practices. Firstly, analytical marketing capabilities harness AI's ability to process and analyze complex datasets, enabling marketers to uncover deep insights and make informed strategic decisions. This application of AI in dissecting vast amounts of data to guide marketing strategies is pivotal for tailoring approaches to consumer needs and market trends. Secondly, technological marketing capabilities leverage AI to automate tasks, streamlining efficiency and improving engagement. Simultaneously, they prioritize ethical considerations, addressing concerns like data privacy, security, and bias. This dual focus ensures that marketing strategies not only advance operational goals but also uphold customer rights and trust, reflecting a commitment to ethical technology use. Lastly, strategic efficiency capabilities highlight AI's role in refining marketing operations to be more agile and responsive. This involves leveraging AI to quickly adapt to market changes and consumer behaviors, ensuring that marketing efforts are both efficient and effective.

Our study significantly enriches the discourse on dynamic capabilities (Hunt & Madhavaram, 2020; Kumar et al., 2019; Leemann & Kanbach, 2022; Matarazzo et al., 2021; Teece, 2020; Weaven et al., 2021) by shedding light on AI's role as a pivotal force in shaping these capabilities within the marketing domain. By addressing a critical gap in the literature regarding how dynamic capabilities are operationalized in today's digital landscape, specifically in marketing, our research underscores the imperative for businesses to adopt AI to maintain a competitive advantage in a rapidly evolving, tech-centric market. This work not only clarifies the mechanisms through which AI facilitates the evolution of marketing capabilities but also signals the strategic value of integrating AI into marketing strategies for long-term business success.

By examining how AI has been integrated into businesses and academic aspects of marketing, we acknowledge AI as a disruptive force that is moving business practices away from reactive models and toward predictive ones in key areas of businesses, namely, customer service, retailing, marketing, sales, and service integration. Instances like Amazon Prime Air's drone delivery or Stitch Fix's personalized shopping exemplify this shift from conventional to predictive business operations (Grandinetti, 2020). Such innovations are not only redefining the environment of consumer contacts but are also setting new benchmarks for operational efficiency. Similarly, RedBalloon's adoption of Albert for enhanced customer engagement demonstrates AI's role in harmonizing marketing efforts with sales and service to boost conversion rates. This evolution in business practices reflects a broader trend where AI is increasingly becoming a fundamental force in driving business growth and customer satisfaction.

Despite the academic world's keen interest in the role of AI in marketing, its full potential and ramifications across all marketing roles remain untapped, and scholars are pushing for more in-depth studies to comprehend AI's role in marketing better. This call to action highlights the transformation of AI from a future concept to a contemporary reality that significantly alters marketing tactics and customer behavior, indicating the necessity for continued research into the industry's long-term influence.

4. Research agenda

To inspire the academic community to produce more impactful research in this emerging domain, we developed a research agenda for AI in marketing. Our primary focus was to identify research areas that

have significant managerial relevance for industry practitioners. Leveraging insights from a review of academic literature (e.g., Huang & Rust, 2022b; Plangger et al., 2022; Mariani et al., 2023) and the latest developments in AI technology, we provide a list of potential research topics and consolidate them into six overarching themes. For each theme outlined, we have presented in Table 3 a set of future research questions aimed at propelling more impactful research. These questions are designed to delve into the complexities and explore uncharted areas within each theme, potentially leading to transformative insights. By examining these questions, researchers and practitioners can broaden their understanding and advance the dialogue in the expansive realm of AI-powered marketing strategies.

The first theme examines the impact of AI on decision-making processes, illustrating how AI-generated customer insights contribute to more nuanced customer segmentation and personalization, as well as more seamless relationship management (Taryn, 2023). The role of predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms is emphasized, showcasing their utility in steering targeted marketing strategies (van Esch et al., 2021; Mende et al., 2023). Going forward, there is a need to understand better how marketers can integrate and utilize AI-driven insights to create more effective and competitive marketing offerings while simultaneously overcoming the existing limitations of AI.

Theme two examines automated marketing strategies, where marketers use automation tools to streamline complex tasks, allowing for better use of marketing budgets and more accurate targeting. Such targeting nurtures high-quality leads and frees up resources for strategic work (De Bruyn et al., 2020; Järvinen & Taiminen, 2016). An important consideration here is to investigate how automated strategies, like programmatic advertising and AI-driven conversational tools, can personalize the customer experience without compromising privacy. Additionally, the impact of automation on brand loyalty and customer retention is questioned, with a push for research into the long-term relationship dynamics between automated marketing and consumer allegiance.

Theme three examines how AI, when integrated with extended realities, can significantly enhance customer experiences in real time across industries. The instantaneity and the guidance provided by AI-driven technologies streamline the shopping experiences and set new standards for customer service across various platforms is still uncertain. Additionally, marketers also need guidance on how AI can enable a fluid and cohesive omnichannel experience for customers.

Theme four examines the ethical implications of AI as it becomes increasingly integrated into various industry sectors (e.g., Ettari et al., 2022; Mende et al., 2023; Mishra, 2023). Data privacy and security, algorithmic bias, and discrimination are the focal concerns of AI use. Promising avenues for future research include providing ethical frameworks that can govern the use of AI, strategizing harmonized efforts for human-machine collaboration, and how trust can be established to guarantee equitable and non-discriminatory outcomes for consumers.

Theme five explores the role of AI in measuring marketing performance, highlighting the depth of insights AI can provide beyond traditional post-campaign analysis. Marketers would benefit from reliable and more accurate methods to leverage real-time marketing performance metrics. Additionally, an understanding of the impact of AI-driven metrics on decision-making and strategy development is paramount.

The last theme focuses on the growth opportunities with AI implementation, exploring the implications of early AI adoption versus long-term strategic use. While early adoption of AI can provide immediate benefits and a competitive edge, it does not guarantee a lasting advantage, and long-term success with AI depends on the strategic use of data, continuous learning, and maintaining trust with customers. Due to significant initial investment, marketers need more guidance regarding the financial implications of adopting AI in marketing and what tangible returns they can expect in both the short and long term. This includes comprehensive analyses of potential cost savings, efficiency gains, and

Table 3
A roadmap for future research on the role of AI in marketing.

Research themes	What we know about AI in marketing	What we would like to know
Theme 1: AI-driven customer insights <i>Rating: 4.37</i> <i>Ranking: 3.70</i>	Aids in <ol style="list-style-type: none"> the development of customer segmentation and personalization the establishment of a seamless relationship management the generation of targeted marketing strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can AI-driven insights (e.g., CRM for customer segmentation and personalization) be leveraged to better predict customer purchasing behaviors in varying market conditions? What are the limitations of current AI technologies in deriving actionable customer insights, and how might these be overcome? How do AI-driven customer insights impact the development and evolution of product offerings in competitive markets?
Theme 2: Automated marketing strategies <i>Rating: 4.10</i> <i>Ranking: 3.65</i>	Aids in <ol style="list-style-type: none"> better use of marketing budgets more accurate targeting generating high-quality leads prioritizing strategic work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent can automated marketing strategies (e.g., programmatic advertising, chatbots, and virtual assistants) personalize customer interactions without compromising privacy? How do automated marketing strategies impact long-term brand loyalty and customer retention? What are the key challenges in integrating AI into traditional marketing strategies, and how can these challenges be mitigated?
Theme 3: Enhancing customer experiences <i>Rating: 4.20</i> <i>Ranking: 3.60</i>	Aids in <ol style="list-style-type: none"> extending realities delivering real-time experiences streamlining shopping experiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can AI be utilized to create more interactive and personalized customer experiences across different industries and platforms, such as Metaverses and spatial computing? What is the impact of AI (e.g., in real-time customer assistance) on customer satisfaction, and how does it compare to traditional customer interaction methods? How can AI contribute to creating seamless omnichannel customer experiences?
Theme 4: Ethical implications <i>Rating: 5.28</i> <i>Ranking: 3.13</i>	Issues that continue to receive attention include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> data privacy and security algorithmic bias discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What ethical frameworks can be developed to govern the use of AI in marketing, ensuring fairness and transparency? How do the ethical implications (e.g., data privacy and security, algorithmic bias and discrimination) of AI affect consumer trust, and what measures can be taken to build and maintain this trust?

Table 3 (continued)

Research themes	What we know about AI in marketing	What we would like to know
Theme 5: Measuring marketing performance <i>Rating: 4.93</i> <i>Ranking: 3.75</i>	Aids in <ol style="list-style-type: none"> deploying marketing campaigns delivering experiences post-campaign analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the long-term ethical implications of data collection and analysis using AI in marketing? How can AI (e.g., AI-powered analytics tools and real-time performance tracking) be leveraged to provide more accurate real-time marketing performance metrics? What are the challenges in measuring marketing performance using AI, and how can these challenges be addressed? How does AI-driven marketing performance measurement impact decision-making and strategy development?
Theme 6: Growth opportunities with AI implementation <i>Rating: 4.70</i> <i>Ranking: 3.18</i>	Aids in <ol style="list-style-type: none"> assessing the implications of early AI adoption providing competitive advantage continuous usage of data-driven marketing campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the cost–benefit tradeoffs (e.g., early adoption benefits of AI) in implementing AI-driven marketing strategies compared to traditional marketing strategies? How do the costs of implementing and maintaining AI in marketing compare to the benefits derived in terms of ROI? How can companies evaluate the cost-effectiveness and ROI of AI investments in their marketing strategies for long-term advantages?

Notes: “Rating” pertains to the average importance score on a seven-point scale, where seven is the most important. “Ranking” pertains to the average importance ranking on a six-point scale, where a lower number signifies greater importance.

revenue growth opportunities enabled by AI-driven marketing strategies. Additionally, marketers require clear metrics and benchmarks to evaluate the effectiveness of AI implementations and track ROI over time. With proper guidance and insights, marketers can make informed decisions about integrating AI technologies into their marketing efforts, maximizing the value of their investments, and achieving sustainable business growth.

Overall, it has become clear that the intersection of AI and marketing is not just a trend but a paradigm shift, one that requires marketers to be agile, informed, and strategic in their adoption of these powerful tools. This shift demands businesses to adapt to AI-driven marketing and actively engage in shaping the process of its evolution. At the current stage of AI, success lies in a company’s ability to integrate AI with human insight and strategic vision. The future of marketing will be defined by those who can harness AI’s potential responsibly and creatively, ensuring that technology augments rather than replaces the human touch that remains at the heart of all marketing endeavors.

5. Practical implications

Although AI adoption in marketing has aided businesses in enhancing customer experience and increasing brand awareness, quantifying these metrics remains a challenging endeavor. Consequently, this leads to a fundamental question: How can we convincingly

advocate for the adoption of AI in marketing practices? To address this, managers must focus on a blend of qualitative and quantitative evidence when exploring AI's impact. This can include case studies showing clear before-and-after comparisons of AI implementation alongside metrics such as improved customer engagement rates, increased conversion rates, and enhanced efficiency in marketing operations. Emphasizing AI's ability to analyze vast datasets for insights that drive targeted marketing strategies can also be persuasive. Additionally, discussing AI's role in providing a competitive edge and its scalability to adapt to evolving market trends can further solidify the argument for its integration into marketing strategies.

For example, Domino's Pizza is a simple yet interesting example of addressing the challenge of advocating for AI in marketing practices. Domino's Pizza effectively demonstrates AI's role in marketing through enhanced order and delivery processes (Garg, 2023). Their use of AI for early pizza preparation and route optimization exemplifies operational efficiency and customer experience improvement. Additionally, Coca-Cola's vending machines incorporate AI to enhance the customer experience. These machines, equipped with AI, offer personalized product recommendations and promotions tailored to the specific location and customer preferences (Rahman, 2019). This not only improves the vending experience but also provides Coca-Cola with valuable consumer data, further refining its marketing and product placement strategies. Both Domino's and Coca-Cola's innovative use of AI showcases its potential to transform customer interactions and a better brand experience. These instances exemplify the innovative and useful application of AI in marketing, showcasing how the technology can significantly enhance marketing strategies and initiatives. Table 4 presents some use cases of AI's role in marketing operations.

To determine the practical importance of each identified marketing theme and to complement our literature review, we surveyed 40 marketing professionals in companies actively implementing or considering AI in their marketing strategies. Survey respondents were asked to rate how important AI is to each marketing theme regarding their business performance (1 = Not important at all, 7 = Extremely important). Respondents were provided with a brief description of each theme. The themes were presented separately and were randomized across respondents to mitigate primacy and recency effects. Next, all themes were presented on a single screen, and respondents were asked to rank the themes in terms of their importance as we advance into the era of AI marketing, with 1 being the most important and 6 being the least important. The six themes were presented in a randomized manner. The mean scores for ratings ranged from 4.10 to 5.28, while the rankings ranged from 3.13 to 3.75 (see Fig. 1 and Table 3).

The survey findings indicate a diverse range of importance and priorities assigned to each theme. The theme with the highest rating was "Ethical Implications," scoring 5.28, which suggests a significant emphasis on the ethical considerations of AI in marketing. As companies increasingly adopt AI technologies for their numerous benefits, managers acknowledge the potential harm AI systems can cause, such as perpetuating biases, infringing on privacy, or making erroneous decisions. This concern becomes more pronounced as governments and regulatory bodies scrutinize AI technologies and enact legislation to ensure their responsible use. Moreover, customers, investors, and stakeholders expect firms to adhere to ethical standards to alleviate fears and skepticism surrounding AI, fostering greater acceptance and integration into society. In contrast, "Measuring Marketing Performance," while rated as highly important, had less of a priority among the professionals. This indicates a significant emphasis on the ethical aspects of AI in marketing and suggests a potential area for future research and focus while recognizing the value of performance measurement in the field.

Themes such as "AI-driven Customer Insights," "Automated Marketing Strategies," and "Enhancing Customer Experiences" received moderate importance ratings (4.37, 4.10, and 4.20, respectively). This suggests a balanced acknowledgment of their significance in AI-driven

Table 4

Application examples of AI being used for different marketing activities.

Themes	Subdimensions	Use Cases
AI-driven customer insights	Predictive analytics	AT&T and Verizon use AI-driven predictive analytics to forecast customer churn by analyzing customer data, usage patterns, and sentiment. Additionally, these telecom giants leverage AI predictive analytics for network optimization and proactively anticipating service challenges, resulting in improved customer experiences.
	Customer segmentation and personalization	Uber uses AI algorithms to segment customers and offer personalized promotions, discounts, and ride recommendations. By analyzing a user's ride history, location, and preferences, Uber can propose popular destinations, nearby dining options, and convenient pickup locations. This results in enhanced user engagement and an enriched and informed experience with the service.
Automated Marketing Strategies	Programmatic advertising	Google employs AI-powered Smart Bidding to optimize ad campaigns. Advertisers set ad campaign objectives, and AI algorithms dynamically adapt bids for optimal results. Google also harnesses AI for accurate audience targeting and ad relevance, improving click-through rates and ensuring that ads are shown to the most appropriate audience, enhancing overall ad quality and engagement.
	AI driven Chatbots and virtual assistants	Amtrak's virtual assistant streamlines ticket booking by allowing users to conveniently search schedules, check ticket availability, and make reservations. Furthermore, chatbots offer 24/7 customer support and immediate response to common queries, enhancing the passengers' overall experience.
Enhancing Customer Experience	Extended Realities and Spatial Computing	Companies like Meta and NVIDIA leverage AI for diverse applications, such as facial recognition, voice and speech recognition, and image recognition, to create immersive experiences. In the case of social VR environments such as Meta Horizon, AI-powered avatars use natural language processing and emotion recognition to make interactions more human-like. The generative adversarial networks allow NIVIDA to apply synthesized high-quality images and textures to 3D models for VR and AR applications.
	Real-time customer assistance	Salesforce's Einstein AI analyzes customer behavior, preferences, and interaction history data in real time and automatically directs customers to the most suitable agents, considering their expertise and availability.

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Themes	Subdimensions	Use Cases
Ethical Implications	Data Privacy and Security	Additionally, it provides agents with recommended responses for efficient customer support. Sift employs AI-driven biometric authentication methods, such as facial recognition, fingerprint scanning, and voice recognition, to help safeguard against data breaches and mitigate unauthorized access. Furthermore, it also analyses user behavior patterns to detect anomalies that may indicate fraudulent activity.
	Algorithmic Bias and Discrimination	Accenture has developed AI-driven tools that assess AI models for bias and discrimination, identifying disparities in predictions across demographics. They also provide metrics and measures for quantifying model fairness, enabling comparisons across groups. Pymetrics, on the other hand, uses neuroscience-based AI algorithms to match job seekers with positions that best fit their cognitive and emotional strengths rather than demographic factors.
Measuring Marketing Performance	AI-powered analytics tools	Hilton employs IBM Watson (a suite of AI-powered technologies) for an AI-powered concierge service that offers individualized recommendations to guests through in-room devices. By analyzing guest preferences, Watson empowers Hilton to fine-tune room amenities and services to cater to each visitor's unique preferences. In addition, Hilton leverages Watson's insights to drive data-informed decision-making, influencing marketing, pricing, and resource allocation based on market trends and customer behavior.
	Real-time performance tracking	Tableau utilizes natural language processing (NLP) for user-friendly data inquiries with real-time visualizations. The platform offers AI-powered connectors for real-time data integration, while AI-driven data alerts promptly notify users of significant data changes, enabling timely responses.
Growth opportunities with AI implementation	Early adoption benefits	Tesla's early integration of AI to advance autonomous driving capabilities set them apart within the automotive sector. The Autopilot and Full Self-Driving (FSD) systems heavily rely on AI models, which continue to advance due to the rich data gathered from real-world driving scenarios. Their emphasis on AI has not only improved safety but also heightened convenience, establishing them as an industry leader.
	Long term benefits	Delta Air leverages AI to automate time-consuming tasks, resulting in reduced human

Table 4 (continued)

Themes	Subdimensions	Use Cases
		labor and costs while simultaneously enhancing resource allocation and operational efficiency. This strategic adoption of AI allows the airline to offer competitive prices and deliver dependable, enhanced services. DeepMind, on the other hand, leverages AI to process vast amounts of healthcare data, expedite innovation, assist in disease diagnosis, optimize patient care, and predict patient deterioration. Garmin uses AI to assist individuals in health monitoring, offering valuable insights and suggestions for long-term well-being.

marketing, albeit not as top priorities compared to ethical implications. This underscores managers' understanding of the importance of responsible AI implementation for long-term organizational success and sustainability. However, they exercise caution, prioritizing a comprehensive understanding of risks, ROI assessment, and addressing employee concerns before full implementation. Interestingly, "Growth opportunities with AI implementation" had a relatively high rating of 4.70 and ranked second, reflecting that managers are aware of both the immediate benefits and long-term advantages of AI adoption. Hence, future researchers can play a valuable role in supporting managers who are cautiously implementing AI technologies by (1) developing decision support tools and models to assist managers in evaluating the costs, benefits, and risks of AI implementation, (2) helping employees transition to new roles and responsibilities by identifying the skills and competencies needed to work effectively with AI systems, and (3) developing methods and tools that can help managers track key performance indicators, assess the impact of AI technologies on business outcomes, and identify areas for improvement and optimization.

As the integration of AI into business systems becomes increasingly prevalent, there is a growing divide among firms regarding its effectiveness (Bankins et al., 2023). In light of this, we advocate for a nuanced approach among managers. Rather than adopting a blanket stance on AI, managers should conduct a thorough analysis to determine its potential impact on their specific business operations. Managers can prioritize AI implementation by identifying areas within marketing operations for streamlined processes and improved outcomes. For example, customer insights exemplify this, where AI has yielded tangible benefits as it empowers marketers by understanding behaviors, anticipating needs, and optimizing strategies, thereby revolutionizing marketing with tailored experiences and predictive capabilities.

Despite lingering questions regarding the ethical implications of AI and managers' hesitancy to fully integrate it into marketing operations, as reflected in our survey results, managers can address these concerns by prioritizing data quality, collection, and management. This ensures that AI algorithms have access to accurate and relevant information, enabling them to generate meaningful insights and drive effective marketing strategies. By investing in robust data practices, managers can enhance the trustworthiness and reliability of AI-driven decision-making processes, ultimately fostering greater confidence in the integration of AI within their marketing operations. Moreover, firms should prioritize transparency, fairness, and accountability in AI implementation. This includes transparently disclosing AI usage, ensuring fairness in algorithm design, and establishing clear accountability structures. Additionally, managers should be open to investing in robust AI-powered analytics tools and platforms. By investing in reliable AI technologies, managers can position their organizations for greater

agility, innovation, and competitiveness in the market.

6. Conclusion

The study emphasizes AI's growing role in marketing, exploring its influence on decision-making, customer experience, and operational efficiency. AI's potential to revolutionize marketing is discussed through analytical, technological, and strategic capabilities. Despite AI's transformative potential, its full impact across marketing roles remains untapped. The research agenda proposes six themes for impactful research, including AI's impact on decision-making, automated marketing strategies, AI in extended realities, ethical implications, measuring marketing performance with AI, and the growth opportunities with AI implementation. The intersection of AI and marketing demands strategic adoption and human insight, ensuring technology enhances rather than replaces the human touch in marketing efforts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Waqar Nadeem: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **V Kumar:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Abdul R. Ashraf:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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None.

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